

HeriTACE

Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.1: Case-study Selection at Building and Neighbourhood Levels is a report that forms the foundation for further investigation in the HeriTACE project. It is essential for the activities in work packages 2, 3, and 4, and is particularly important for the efforts in work package 5. The primary aim of work package 5 is to develop a holistic assessment framework for the renovation of heritage townhouses, considering not only energy use but also heritage value, user comfort, functionality, and other factors. A holistic approach requires a transdisciplinary understanding of the heritage building and its context, which is the primary objective of this report.

The HeriTACE project focuses on small to medium-sized heritage townhouses built before 1945, a building type prevalent in many European cities. The research is conducted simultaneously in four countries: Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Italy, each with its distinct variations of this specific building type. To ensure the replicability of renovation strategies, a selection of the most representative archetypes is made for each country, upon which various strategies can later be tested.

An archetype is a typical and often repeated principle of a building design with clear characteristics. An archetype serves as a prototype for designing building with the same function.

Additionally, representative neighbourhoods and case studies are selected for measurements, interviews, and tests.

A case study building is a real-life subject of investigation. The case study is a variation or adjustment of the archetype to the specific context in which it is built.

The selection of these archetypes, case studies and neighbourhoods is extensively documented in this report, from a historical, sociological and architectural perspective.

Belgium

In Belgium the typology of the masonry heritage terraced townhouses from the period 1800-1918 is selected, based on the most prevalent type of historical building in historical city centres. The research is focused on the city of Ghent, where the neighbourhoods and case studies are located. The district around the Sint-Michielsplein is chosen as primary research focus, while city blocks around the northern section of the Vlaanderenstraat are also documented. The district around the Sint-Michielsplein is an organically developed neighbourhood with the masonry heritage terraced townhouse as most prevalent archetype but also with the presence of older and newer buildings (e.g. a 20th-century underground parking garage). The northern section of the Vlaanderenstraat is a shopping district that emerged as a result of the expansion and sanitation of the city around 1900. The more uniform Vlaanderenstraat was constructed by cutting through existing city fabric. The buildings are all erected around the same period (and are of the studied typology).

The selection of the archetypes was made based on extensive literature research (both historical and recent) with input from heritage experts and the analysis of archival building permits of Ghent, Brussels and Antwerp. An informed and representative selection could be derived. Four archetypes are identified: the middle-class townhouse, the private mansion, the multi-family townhouse, and the modest house. Among these, the middle-class townhouse is the most commonly found archetype.

Three case study buildings are selected, of which two are of the middle-class townhouse archetype (Hertstraat and Meersstraat) and one of the private mansion archetype (Hoogstraat). These townhouses are selected because of their compliance with the archetype and the willingness and interest of the inhabitants in participating in the project. A general description of the architectural, constructive and technical conditions of the case studies is provided based on archive documentation and site visits. Beside these three case studies, about 25 other heritage townhouses are identified as potential interesting cases for more (in depth) analyses, measurements or interviews when needed.

Norway

Cultural heritage and historic environments play a crucial role in shaping the identity, and serve as rich source of knowledge, experiences, and economic value. The small, unpretentious dwellings were home to labourers, artisans, and their families. Their modest size and simple design reflect the financial limitations faced by these working-class individuals.

In Norway, the studied typology is the wooden log heritage townhouse from the period 1800-1945. The case area neighbourhood in Bakklandet, Trondheim, represents a relatively large area of a cultural heritage environment, consisting of detached and semi-detached houses. The use of wood as the main material in constructions is deeply rooted in Nordic building traditions and practices but is also found in several locations across Northern and Central Europe (mainly alpine areas). Many wooden heritage environments are, and have been for decades, threatened by challenges such as decay, lack of maintenance, unsuccessful energy efficiency measures, urban development pressure, and changed user requirements.

Bakklandet neighbourhood is a district within the main core of Trondheim where people live, work, and interact. It is characterized by shared physical features, social connections, and a sense of community, i.a. due to the conformity of the small, two-storey wooden residential buildings. In the neighbourhood, the individual houses and buildings contribute to the overall character and functionality. Bakklandet's heritage values lie not only in its architectural features but also in the collective memory of the working-class lives that unfolded in the neighbourhood. It stands as a reminder of the human stories embedded in the built environment, connecting us to the past and enriching our understanding of history. The individual buildings in Bakklandet hold significant cultural heritage value.

The chosen archetype for this project is the wooden log townhouse. Although the number of traditional log buildings in Norway is not extensive, they hold significant cultural value. Adapting these structures for modern comfort without compromising their heritage value is challenging.

Estonia

In Estonia wood has been the main traditional building material over centuries. Most of the remaining wooden apartment buildings that originate from the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century are forming well-preserved entities (Arumägi, 2015). Large-scale urban areas of wooden apartment buildings, that are still preserved in Tallinn, Tartu or other cities and towns in Estonia, tend to be quite rare in the cities of Europe and have been listed as milieu valuable areas.

The area of Uus-Maailm (New World) in Tallinn was developed during the 1st half of the 20th century as two- or three story wooden buildings of Lender and Tallinn types were built. The bombings of 1944 destroyed a large part of the district and massive brick apartment buildings in neo-classical style were built during 1940s and 50s (the Stalinist type) in its place. Thus, the development of this area that is now considered of milieu value consists of a variety of building types of different size and construction materials allowing to follow and retell the historical events that have formed Tallinn.

The 5 case study buildings were selected to be representative for both the culturally valuable archetypes of the neighbourhood (the Lender *and* Tallinn type wooden buildings and the Stalinist type masonry buildings). The building envelope solutions, service systems and modifications in the current case study buildings also cover a wide variety of possibilities found in Uus Maailm.

Italy

Masonry houses before 1945 represent over 5% of historic buildings in Italy and are especially representative in the northern part of the country. They are characterized by their robust structural systems, typically composed of brick or stone walls with wooden beams supporting the floors and roofs. The choice of materials often depended on local availability, with brick most common in urban areas and stone prevalent in rural settings.

According to this premise, it was decided to work on the masonry building heritage in Northern Italy, considering its maintenance as crucial for the protection of the historical and cultural identity of a part of the Italian heritage.

The chosen study neighbourhood is the UNESCO area of the city of Mantova (UNESCO World Heritage since 2008). The city's original settlement assets dates to the 15th and 16th centuries; despite that the city centre has undergone urban and architectural transformations in the following centuries, its morphological relationship with the pre-existing buildings has not changed.

In the Mantovan area, four main archetypes were identified: Gothic lot (considered also in its variant as porticoed-gothic lot houses); Extended building typology; Palazzetto and Courtyard building. The selection of the archetypes was made based on extensive literature research and considering local superintendence's indications.

Five case studies were selected so to be representative of the exposed archetypes. About these buildings, despite one of them is positioned outside the city walls, it presents the same formal, constructive and material peculiarities of the indicated archetypes of masonry buildings indagated in the Mantova historical centre.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
EU	European Union
HDD	Heating degree days
HeriTACE	Future-proofing HERItage Buildings by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and SpACE
IAQ	Indoor air quality
PGT	Territorial Government Plan [Piani di Governo del Territorio]
R²ES	Renewable and Residual Energy Sources
RCP	Representative concentration pathways
SEFRAK	The national register of cultural heritage in Norway (SEkretariatet For Registrering Av faste Kulturminner)
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WP	Work package
WW	World War

Introduction

The ambitions of the European Union (EU) are substantial: to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus aim to achieve a sustainable, aesthetic, and inclusive society through transdisciplinary collaboration and innovation. The necessity and value of sustainable use and transformation of existing built environment has been emphasized in research for a long time (Fufa et al., 2021). However, one of the most significant challenges in this transition will be the renovation wave of our housing stock, which accounts for 27% of the final energy use of the EU (Eurostat, 2022). Historic cities in Europe present an additional difficulty. It is evident that the historically valuable buildings in these cities must be preserved while respecting and considering the inherent heritage and societal values. However, the methods for achieving this while maintaining climate neutrality are often less clear.

The HeriTACE project investigates how we can future-proof our heritage buildings in a manner that bridges the gap between heritage restrictions and environmental ambitions. The project focuses specifically on small to medium-sized heritage townhouses pre-dating 1945. Achieving the ambitious goal of climate-neutrality requires a transdisciplinary team to consider all aspects of renovation: heritage value, energy use, user comfort, functionality, cost-effectiveness, and waste management. Heritage restrictions often preclude generic solutions, necessitating innovative approaches to insulation, heating, ventilation, and heat/cold generation.

To develop broadly applicable solutions, this research is conducted simultaneously in four European countries: Belgium, Norway, Estonia, and Italy, for one city in each country in particular. In Belgium, Ghent is considered, in Norway the city of Trondheim, in Estonia Tallinn and in Italy, the city of Mantova (see figure 0.1). The buildings in these countries differ significantly from one another. The aim of this report is to explain the building types considered in each country. National history, socio-economic evolutions, differences in construction logic, and local climate profoundly influence past building practices. The result is a comprehensive and detailed overview of the main characteristics (and their causes) of the various building types, neighbourhoods, and cities.

Figure 0.1: Map of Europe displaying the selected cities for the HeriTACE project: Ghent (Belgium), Trondheim (Norway), Tallinn (Estonia) and Mantova (Italy).

The report follows a consistent structure for each country where the research is conducted. First, the relevance of the considered building type, or typology, is demonstrated within the national context. Subsequently, a neighbourhood is described where part of the project will be implemented. The typology is then further subdivided into common archetypes specific to the country in question. Finally, specific case studies are listed, where measurements, tests, and interviews will be conducted later in the heriTACE project.

The archetypes and neighbourhoods described in this report form the foundation for the rest of the HeriTACE project. The neighbourhoods will be used to investigate energy production on a larger scale than the individual building, with all the opportunities and constraints associated with this scale level. The selected archetypes will be used to create detailed simulation models, allowing renovation solutions to be tested virtually. The data generated from the case studies will serve as input for various aspects, from simulation models to heritage assessments and user experience analyses. This information will contribute to giving insights into how energy efficiency measures may be implemented in cultural heritage buildings and neighbourhoods without compromising the inherent heritage values.

1. Belgium

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1.1. Relevance of studied typology

In Belgium, the studied typology is the masonry heritage terraced townhouse from the period 1800-1918. The research is focused on the city of Ghent, but this typology is also frequently occurring in other major and minor cities in Belgium. The considered period is indeed pertinent, as Ghent (and other cities) experienced a colossal growth in the number of dwellings during that timeframe. Between 1834 and 1915, the number of dwellings in Ghent surged from 12,500 to 38,669, more than a tripling over an 80-year span (Fris, 1920). Contrastingly, in the period from 1662 to 1834, spanning nearly 200 years, the housing stock in Ghent increased by merely 6,000 dwellings. Particularly in the latter half of the 19th century, Ghent witnessed an unprecedented expansion.

A significant portion of this historic housing stock remains present in the city today. Of the more than 95,000 buildings in Ghent today, approximately 28% (or 27,000 buildings) are terraced townhouses constructed before 1918 (STATBEL, 2023). This percentage includes buildings from before 1800, as well as structures that may be considered less valuable from a heritage perspective, such as workers' houses. The majority of Ghent's inner city has been designated by the government as a residential area with cultural, historical, and/or aesthetic value. Approximately 10,000 terraced townhouses built between 1800-1918 are located within this area (FOD Financiën, 2022), meaning that any significant modification on the exterior requires an advice from the Urban Archaeology and Heritage Conservation Service of Ghent. It can be assumed that these townhouses, which constitute about 10% of Ghent's building stock, possess a certain heritage value and are therefore in scope of this research. The Urban Archaeology and Heritage Conservation Service of Ghent stipulates that at least 2% of Ghent's building stock consists of terraced townhouses that are either protected as a monument or listed as ascertained built heritage (Flemish Heritage Agency, 2024). Protected monuments are subject to stringent protection regulations, necessitating approval from the Flemish Heritage Agency and the Urban Archaeology and Heritage Conservation Service of Ghent for any alterations, but also any modification to ascertained built heritage needs approval from the Urban Archaeology and Heritage Conservation Service of Ghent.

This selected townhouse typology is not specific to Ghent, but also commonly present in the other cities of Belgium. In Brussels (Brussels-Capital Region), the biggest agglomeration of the country, the masonry heritage terraced townhouse built between 1800 and 1914 is the most common historic typology: about 58% of the dwellings built before 1945 was of the terraced townhouse type (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). Of the 195,000 buildings that are present in Brussels today, 47,000 buildings are terraced buildings built before 1918, representing 24% of the building stock (STATBEL, 2023). The whole city centre within the Medieval city walls as well as big parts of the neighbouring municipalities are defined as 'areas of cultural, historical or aesthetic value' which again means an advice of the heritage service is mandatory prior to any alterations. At least 13,000 terraced townhouses (7%) are listed on the Brussels inventory of architectural heritage of which more than 350 are protected as a monument (Urban.Brussels, 2024).

The studied typology occurs frequently in other major cities that underwent similar population growth and societal changes as in Ghent or Brussels. The heritage townhouse is prevalent in cities like Antwerp, Charleroi, Liège or Mons. Further, this typology also is present in smaller cities or towns like Ostend, Mechelen, Leuven or Namur. The typology of the masonry heritage terraced townhouses represents between 3.8% and 9.8% of the Belgian building stock (STATBEL, 2023)¹.

Figure 1.1: Map of Belgium with indication of the 20 cities where the masonry heritage terraced townhouse are the most prevalent (STATBEL, 2023). The bigger the circle, the more townhouses are present.

1.2. Neighbourhood selection

Ghent's development into a city began in the Middle Ages. Agricultural surpluses and its strategic location at the confluence of the Leie and Scheldt rivers fostered commercial and artisanal prosperity. Around 1300, Ghent had become one of the largest and most important cities in Western Europe (Boone, 2010). The city's second significant expansion occurred during the Industrial Revolution, when Ghent emerged as a major industrial centre in the 19th century, continuing into the 20th century. The demand for labour led to a doubling of the population between 1801 and 1866. Consequently, the built area of the city doubled by 1880 and tripled by 1913 (Deneckere, 2010). Old houses were replaced or modernised. However, large urban planning projects inspired by the tabula rasa - or 'clean slate' - urbanism of 19th-century Paris, introduced new street layouts that cut through the medieval

¹ 3.8% of the Belgian building stock are masonry heritage terraced townhouses built between 1900 and 1918. 9.8% of the Belgian building stock are masonry heritage terraced townhouses built before 1900 (and thus includes also older buildings).

core, creating new subdivisions in the form of new urban boulevards. These avenues were all adorned with the formal facades of the bourgeoisie. As a result, Ghent was rapidly developing entire neighbourhoods, even beyond the medieval boundaries (Cleppe & Uyttenhove, 2010; Roose, 1996), exemplifying a common type of European urban development during the research period of 1800-1918.

The 'Sint-Michielsplein' site serves as the first and main research neighbourhood. The 'Vlaanderenstraat - northern section' site is the second. Both sites are indicated on Figure 1.18 (section 1.41.4) to give the broader context. The sites are complementary in terms of their urban development and building typology. The selection of these sites is based on a dual rationale: they present realistic and sufficiently complex issues, and the challenges encountered in these neighbourhoods are similar to those faced by districts in other European cities. In both areas, the different archetypes (which will be elaborated upon in section 1.3) are well-represented.

1.2.1. Sint-Michielsplein

The study area is located around the Sint-Michielsplein ('St Michael's Church Square'). The district is further delineated by Ingelandgat to the west, Wilderoosstraat to the south, and Onderbergen to the east. This neighbourhood lies in the medieval heart of the city, near the former port at the Gras- and Korenlei (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-d). The area has developed historically and organically, with buildings from various periods and a mixture of functions and building types that intersect and blend together. The neighbourhood is dominated by the Gothic Sint-Michielskerk, whose construction began in 1440. Its western tower borders the eponymous square, which still contains remnants of the former cemetery, while its rear faces the river Leie (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-e).

Figure 1.2: Map of the neighbourhood 'Sint-Michielsplein' in Ghent (Maton, 2024).

The buildings surrounding the square and in the rest of the block predominantly consist of historic heritage dwellings from various construction periods and typologies (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-f). By screening the existing buildings using the Flemish scientific inventory of heritage buildings, it was determined that the researched typology is widely present. The masonry heritage terraced townhouses present in this neighbourhood span the entire research period, dating from the first half of the 19th century to the first quarter of the 20th century. Due to the organic growth of this site, some of this 19th-century townhouses have an older core or are renovated older houses. Most of the heritage houses feature typical plastered and painted facades and have retained their residential function, however not necessarily without later adaptations or modernisations. The only building that diverges from this historical context is a 20th-century underground parking garage with an above-ground office building. This structure is located on the southern side of the square and extends into the adjacent block.

The choice of this neighbourhood is based on the presence of several possible opportunities that might facilitate the energy transition and the challenge to use local renewable and residual energy sources (R²ES). Investigating what these opportunities can effectively bring in a heritage context will result in valuable insights for replication cases.

Firstly, the presence of the underground parking garage must be considered. This parking facility (and part of the office building) is owned by the City of Ghent, with co-ownership for the common areas. This allows for a realistic and accessible examination of how this non-heritage infrastructure can be utilized to make the surrounding heritage buildings fossil-free, for instance, as a heat source or location for energy storage. The widespread presence of 20th-century parking garages (deep) in the historical centres of European cities strongly motivates the selection of this site due to the potential transferability of the results.

Secondly, the proximity of the river Leie presents an additional opportunity. The water from this river can be used as a heat source for individual or collective heat pump systems, or for regenerating the soil in the context of geothermal heating for heating-dominated buildings (e.g. during summer when the biodiversity in rivers benefits from being cooled). Finally, the selection of this site can also be used as leverage for a subsequent research trajectory into the energy-efficient retrofitting of 'challenging' large historical monuments or buildings, such as the Sint-Michielskerk in this instance.

1.2.2. Vlaanderenstraat (northern section)

The central avenue in the second study area is the northern section of the Vlaanderenstraat, between house numbers 1 and 85. The rest of the site is delineated by the Notarisstraat, the Lange Boomgaardstraat, the Brabantdam, the H. Lippensplein in the south and the François Laurentplein in the west. The Vlaanderenstraat bears witness to the 19th-century urban planning vision. It was drawn in 1883 straight through an existing neighbourhood. This intentionally designed shopping street connected the former South Station with the historic city centre and its monuments (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-g; Roose, 1996). The current homes in the Vlaanderenstraat were erected following this new urban development and are all constructed within a limited timeframe, precisely during the period when the original built-up area of Ghent tripled (Dambryne et al., 1992).

Figure 1.3: Map of the neighbourhood 'Vlaanderenstraat' in Ghent (Maton, 2024).

The buildings that adorn the Vlaanderenstraat frequently belong to the archetype of the middle-class townhouse (see section 1.3.1). These were primarily designed as merchant's houses, with a commercial space on the ground floor and residences above. To this day, this ground-floor commercial function can still be found in most of these houses, although the interior is often modified to fit modern needs. Additionally, there are buildings with exclusively residential functions. The buildings along this street exhibit very typical elements such as decorated shopfronts, balconies, bay windows, sometimes *entresols* in eclectic and neo styles. There are plastered, natural stone and brick facades. The street view is relatively authentic and cohesive, mainly because of the *tabula rasa* policy of the 19th century. A few 20th-century intrusions interrupt this homogeneous view.

The adjacent Notarisstraat and Lange Boomgaardstraat underwent significant alterations and (re)development simultaneously with the Vlaanderenstraat. The archetype of the 'middle-class townhouse' is also widely represented here. The street views of both streets remain relatively authentic and homogeneous (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-c, n.d.-b). The section of Brabantdam that intersects with the Vlaanderenstraat is part of an older existing street. However, its northern side was also altered as part of the same urban planning campaign. Numerous middle-class townhouses can be found here as well (Flemish Heritage Agency, n.d.-a).

The choice of this neighbourhood is also driven by the presence of several challenges and opportunities regarding the energy system that can be found in this area. Firstly, there is the proximity of the river Muinschelde, that could be used as a heat source for heat pump systems or regeneration of borefields. Furthermore, the diversity of functions that are present in the buildings in the studied building blocks leads to different (and complementary) demand profiles. On the scale of a neighbourhood, there is consequently

an opportunity of exchanging energy between the different functions and thus sharing energy (and its conversion and storage). Additionally, the simultaneity of demand can lead to efficiency gains. Finally, just a short distance from the Vlaanderenstraat, an underground parking facility can also be found.

Conversely, this city block gives rise to challenges. The construction of new avenues cutting through old neighbourhoods results in highly dense building blocks with often irregular shapes. The building blocks along Vlaanderenstraat are wedge-shaped with a very small inner area. Most buildings do not have a garden or courtyard in this zone. The plots themselves vary greatly in size, with some corner houses situated on highly challenging parcels. These challenging wedge-shaped building plots are often present in Western European historical city. The strategies and solutions found here can therefore also be applied elsewhere, in Ghent as well as in numerous other European cities.

Lastly, it must be noted that the district heating network of Ghent, supplied by the Luminus gas power plant, is located in the southern part of the considered neighbourhood. Currently, several large buildings are connected to this network, such as the hospital, the university, and a swimming pool, but not the residential buildings around the Vlaanderenstraat. Although the presence of the network could potentially offer an opportunity, the company Luminus has no plans to expand the network and connect it to individual dwellings. Therefore, alternative solutions must be sought.

1.3. Archetype selection

Emerging of a new class: the bourgeoisie

The industrial revolution in the 19th century led to economic development. This not only led to a considerable expansion of the labour force, but also gave rise to a new, influential class: the bourgeoisie. They were the people who benefited from the industrialisation: factory owners, merchants, entrepreneurs, etc., who prospered financially and gained societal prestige. This emergent class distanced itself from the historically dominant classes of the nobility as well as the workers. The bourgeoisie sought to display its newly acquired power and used the city and its architecture to do so. The city became the quintessential site for seeing and being seen (Tyssens et al., 2009).

With the rise of the bourgeoisie, the socio-cultural societal model adapts to accommodate this new dominant class's values (D'haese, 2012). The values of the classic family (mother, father and children) take centre stage: henceforth, the couple sleeps in the same room, and the relationship with the children becomes important again. Each child is allocated their own bedrooms, situated not far from the parental bedroom. Upbringing of children becomes the responsibility of the parents again (often the mother during that period), rather than a governess.

Simultaneously, the relationships between residents (both family members and staff) become less intimate, resulting in increased circulation spaces, *antichambres* and *vestibules* (which are both a sort of hallway). Efforts are made to maintain as much separation as possible between staff and residents, which may lead to distinct service circulation and service areas. There exists a certain tension between the renewed emphasis on the family and the bourgeoisie's desire to display their status (Vandenbreenen & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994). This tension results in a strict division between private and public life within the home. The dining room serves as the exception that confirms the rule (Ledent, 2012). In the dining room, the family now consumes meals together, often with significant guests. This space is utilised to affirm the family's social status, thereby erasing any semblance of domesticity.

Subdivision

The influential French architect and theorist Eugène Viollet-le-Duc delineated three distinct types of modern urban dwellings as early as 1863 in his work *Entretien sur l'architecture*. Likewise, the Belgian architectural magazine *L'émulation* (La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874) refers to the same three types of terraced townhouses: *La maison de bourgeoisie* or middle-class townhouse, *la maison de maître* or private mansion and *la maison de rapport* or multi-family townhouse. Adding to this classification, the Belgian architect Louis Cloquet, who was an architecture professor at Ghent University, introduces a fourth category: *la maison d'employé* or modest house (Cloquet, 1900). Of this four archetypes, the middle-class townhouse is the most prevalent in Ghent, but also in the rest of Belgium (Flemish Heritage Agency, 2024). In the following paragraphs, those four archetypal terraced townhouses will be explained in detail.

1.3.1. Middle-class townhouse

General description

The first archetype of the masonry heritage terraced townhouse is the middle-class townhouse. Those houses of the bourgeoisie are typically single-family houses and constitute of terraced houses that form part of densely constructed city blocks. The high demand for housing also led the bourgeoisie to inhabit relatively narrow but deep plots. The width of a typical bourgeois dwelling was largely influenced by the constructive limitations of that period: the load-bearing capacity of the wooden beams forming the basis for the roof. Consequently, bourgeois houses typically have a width of around 6 meters (Ledent, 2012).

The facade serves as a firm demarcation from the street, representing the residents' face towards the city and contributing to the urban scene of bourgeois life (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). Simultaneously, the facade conceals what unfolds behind it. In the centre of those dense building blocks, the individual gardens of the different middle-class townhouses form an open and green area.

Unlike houses from the 17th and 18th centuries, facades of 19th-century bourgeois residences are invariably unique. The individuality of the bourgeoisie and the social status of the inhabitants should be discernible from the facade (Hooft, 1997). Throughout the 19th and early 20th centuries, facades were executed in several different architectural styles, ranging from Neo-Renaissance and Neo-Gothic to eclectic architecture and Art Nouveau (from the early 20th century onwards). The first three are essentially stylistic revivals of historical architectural styles, which 19th-century architects eagerly employed (Struye, 1973).

Because the facade was pivotal for bourgeois representation, it was often crafted with noble materials. While initially, the facade was typically plastered to protect the underlying materials, from the second half of the 19th century onward, materials such as natural stone, exposed brick, and their combinations were frequently utilized. Additionally, it was adorned with necessary ornamentation: balconies, bay windows, cornices, transoms, pediment crowns, etc. In contrast to the front facade, little attention was paid to the back facade of the building, as it was not oriented towards the city. This facade was functionally constructed, with minimal to no embellishment (D'haese, 2012).

Figure 1.4: Facade (left) and section (right) of a middle class townhouse (Maton, 2024).

A typical middle-class townhouse comprises three levels (sometimes two), characterised by the ground floor being elevated from street level, up to 180 cm, termed as the *bel étage*. Consequently, the basement is partially submerged underground and lighted through a window at street level. These houses are often crowned with gable or mansard roofs. In the facade two or three spans are visible, as shown in Figure 1.4: Facade (left) and section (right) of a middle class townhousefigure 1.4.

Spatial organisation

The constrained width and substantial depth of the plot significantly determine the spatial organisation of the dwelling. A middle-class townhouse, due to its location in the building block as a narrow terraced house, adopts a vertical orientation (Hooft, 1997), with spaces arranged sequentially perpendicular to the street, an *enfilade*. While the architectural styles and facades of these houses may vary, the fundamental spatial arrangement remains largely invariant.

Firstly, this spatial organisation directly reflects bourgeois lifestyle conventions: the inclusion of representative spaces, areas designated for familial seclusion, and quarters for servants (preferably segregated from the principal residents) (Cloquet, 1900). To facilitate this, the dwelling spaces were categorised into primary spaces or living areas and secondary spaces reserved for circulation and supporting functions. In practice, the dwelling is divided into a large span (with a width of two-third of the facade) where the primary spaces are situated and a smaller span (with a width of the remaining one-third of the facade) where the secondary spaces are located, as illustrated in figure 1.5. In the facade, the larger span can consist of one big window or can be further divided and provided with two windows.

Figure 1.5: Division in a broader span on the left side and a smaller span on the right (Maton, 2024).

Secondly, the spatial configuration within the dwelling adheres to a strict hierarchy: spaces closer to the street are inherently more representative, while those situated higher within the dwelling offer increased privacy and intimacy (Ledent, 2012). Consequently, the space within the wider span next to the street at the *bel étage* level is the room through which the inhabitants seek to showcase their societal status. Correspondingly, the height of these spaces is tailored accordingly, with rooms at the *bel étage* being the loftiest, featuring ceiling heights reaching up to 5 meters. Ceilings progressively diminish in height as one ascends higher within the dwelling. The basement level, likewise, features a low ceiling height, as it serves no representative function.

Finally, the structural reality of the 19th century significantly shapes the spatial organisation to a large extent. The construction methods still strongly adhere to the tradition of the previous centuries, namely, wooden houses. Due to the presence of local clay in Belgium and new regulations aimed at preventing disastrous urban fires, bricks were introduced for wall construction. The floors continued to be constructed with wooden frameworks, as did the roofs. In order to mitigate the risk of urban fires, it was prohibited to rest the wooden floor joists on the party walls. Consequently, the facades and partition walls of the *enfilade* became load-bearing structures, and the wooden framework was positioned perpendicular to the street. The depth of the *enfilade* rooms was thus determined by the typical length of these wooden beams, usually around 4.5 meters (Burniat, 2012). An exception to this was the structure of the roof, which was permitted to be supported by the party walls. As previously mentioned, the typical length here was around 6 meters, determining the width of the dwelling.

The distribution of functions for various spaces has been established since the early 19th century, documented extensively in historical sources (Cloquet, 1900; La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874) as well as contemporary literature (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.; D'haese, 2012; Hooft, 1997; Ledent, 2012; Ledent & Porotto, 2023; Vandenbreenen & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994).

Figure 1.6 demonstrates the floor plans of the partially submerged basement, or *souterrain*, which accommodates service areas. Typically, the kitchen occupies the broader span at this level, benefiting from natural light through a street-level window. The narrow span often houses a coal cellar. Additionally, an *enfilade* of spaces is already present within the basement: beyond the kitchen, one typically finds a laundry area and a storage room for provisions, providing rear access to the garden. In the early 19th century, the sanitary facilities were also located here.

Figure 1.6: Floor plans of the basement level of a middle-class townhouse. Variant without annex (left) and with annex (right) (Maton, 2024).

When entering the middle-class townhouse through a very high front door with transoms in the small span, consequently a few (marble) steps must be taken before entering the hallway or *vestibule* (sometimes through a glass double door). At this level of the *bel étage*, the entrance to the rooms in the wider span is provided, as shown in figure 1.7. Those rooms form an *enfilade* of two, occasionally three rooms with a salon at the street side, a dining room behind it and, in more recent cases, a veranda at the garden side. By providing a veranda, daylight can penetrate deeper into the dining room. As previously noted, the most formal and representative room is the salon, designated for hosting visitors. The dining room, while serving as the communal dining space for the family, also functions as an extension of the salon, thereby accommodating additional guests when necessary. Large swinging doors between these two spaces (and the veranda as well) facilitate secondary circulation, supplementing that provided by the *vestibule*. The rooms in the wider span are each equipped with a fireplace to provide the necessary local space heating. In the small span, in continuation of the *vestibule*, a wooden staircase with two flights is located to grant access to the upper floors. To access the garden or the annex (see later) in the back, you must go beneath the intermediate landing of the staircase. On the level of the landing, a toilet could be provided in more recent and comfortable dwellings.

Figure 1.7: Floor plans of the *bel étage* level of a middle-class townhouse. Variant without annex (left) and with annex (right) (Maton, 2024).

Due to the technical constraints of those periods, the load-bearing walls should be placed on top of each other, resulting in floor plans of the upper floors which are a replication of the *bel étage*, with the exception of the veranda. On the upper floor the *enfilade* is limited to only two rooms behind each other. Figure 1.8 shows the floor plans of those upper floors. Within the broader span, two spacious chambers (commonly designated as bedrooms or private salons) are allocated with the same dimensions as the salon and dining room on the *bel étage*. Within the smaller span, situated above the entrance to the dwelling, a smaller room is situated. This room can be equipped as a bedroom, bathroom or office. In some cases, the room at the street side covers the whole width of the building, effacing the division between the two spans. Again, each room is equipped with a fireplace and between the rooms in the wider span, large swinging doors provide a secondary circulation so that servants and inhabitants can be separated as much as possible. Under the mansard or gable roof, the rooms for the servant are located, possibly equipped with dormer windows.

Figure 1.8: Floor plans of the first (left), second (middle) and third floor (right) of a middle-class townhouse in the variation with an annex (Maton, 2024).

It occasionally occurred that the kitchen was not situated in the basement. In instances where a partially submerged basement was impossible thus precluding the provision of natural light, placing the kitchen in the basement was deemed impossible. Consequently, the kitchen would be relocated to the *bel étage* level within the narrow span. It would be accommodated within an annex situated behind the staircase, as shown in figure 1.7. This adjustment facilitated a more functional operation due to its proximity to the dining room, albeit slightly disrupting the hierarchical principle. Moreover, this annex could also encompass additional spaces such as a small office, laundry room, or pantry. Furthermore, this annex could extend to the upper floors, where access would be facilitated via the intermediate landings, and where sanitary facilities often found their place, as illustrated in figure 1.8.

Figure 1.9: Facade variations on a repetitive plan as published by Fernand Salmain from 1908 to 1913 (Ledent & Porotto, 2023).

Transformations

The contemporary mode of living naturally diverges from the organisational principles within middle-class townhouses during the 19th century. Indeed, communal living arrangements with domestic staff have long since ceased, relegating the former servant quarters in the attic to alternate functions such as supplementary bedrooms or mere attic storage.

Furthermore, the kitchen, once relegated to a subordinate position in the basement, has transitioned to a central place within the dwelling. Presently, kitchens are frequently situated within the annex or occupy the space that was formerly designated for the salon or dining room. Additionally, numerous dwellings have undergone modifications, with the addition of a veranda or the construction of entirely new extensions. New and more comfortable bathrooms are placed on the upper levels of the annex or in the rooms in the small span. Meanwhile, the configuration of sleeping quarters typically remains on upper floors, while living spaces remain on the *bel étage*, although exceptions exist wherein all living spaces are relocated to the basement. Such deviations are motivated both by the prospect of direct access to the garden often afforded by the basement level and the cooler temperatures of the lower floor. The scale of these dwellings is nowadays often too large for one family. Consequently, a considerable part of these middle-class townhouses undergoes conversion into multi-family dwellings, featuring distinct apartments on each level. In Ghent, which is the biggest Flemish student city (Vlaanderen, 2024), a lot of these townhouses are also converted into student accommodation, featuring multiple student rooms on each floor.

Variants

Undoubtedly, it should be acknowledged that this archetype is not 'set in stone', and permutations are possible concerning factors such as the number of levels, the width of the building, the elevation of the *bel étage*, or the roof shape. Nevertheless, according to literature (Ledent & Porotto, 2023) there exist two variants of the archetype that merit special consideration due to their frequent occurrence and their own distinctive logic.

The first is the corner house. The geometric street patterns and the smaller yet denser building blocks of the new urban development contribute to the proliferation of such corner solutions. Precisely because of the specificity inherent in these solutions, obtaining a clear and unambiguous understanding of the spatial organisation of the corner house proves challenging. However, Ledent (2012) tries: corner houses often lack (or have limited) connections to the inner area of the city block behind them, necessitating reliance solely on the street-facing facades for natural light. Moreover, a clear distinction between front and rear facades becomes blurred. Instead of an *enfilade* of rooms stretching from front to back facade, the various spaces are arrayed along the street-facing facade, revolving around the hallway (as depicted in figure 1.11). Efforts are made to uphold hierarchy within the dwelling: the higher and more towards the courtyard, the more intimate the spaces. Nevertheless, the specific context also engenders somewhat unconventional connections (e.g., between bedroom and salon). It is clear that a corner allows for a freer interpretation of the archetype (Hooft, 1997), which also results in a range of diverse solutions for the facades: one facade is deemed primary while the other remains blind; both facades are treated as if they were the facade of a middle-class townhouse; or no second facade is provided, only a garden wall. Lastly, it is also common to find a commercial space on the ground floor, with apartments above (see subsequent paragraphs).

Figure 1.11: Floor plan of one of the upper floors of a corner house (Maton, 2024).

The second variant is the merchant's house. In this type of dwelling, the ground floor is occupied by a commercial space (shop, cafeteria, pharmacist, etc.), either partially or completely. The merchant's house is missing the elevated *bel étage*, because the shop should be directly accessible from the street. Consequently, the absence of a partially submerged basement renders spaces such as kitchens or laundry rooms unfeasible in this place. Instead, the cellar is primarily designated for storage purposes. Analogous to occurrences in the middle-class townhouse, the kitchen is relocated to an annex. An often elaborately ornamented storefront provides entry to the shop, often supplemented by a separate entrance to the residential quarters (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.), as shown in figure 1.10. In exceptional cases, access to the dwelling may be situated at the rear of the shop. Furthermore, the archetypal layout of the middle-class townhouse persists, albeit commencing from the first floor upwards.

Figure 1.10: Floor plan of the ground floor of a merchant's house (Maton, 2024).

1.3.2. Private mansion

General description

The second archetype of the masonry heritage terraced townhouse is the private mansion. While the middle-class townhouse was inhabited by the bourgeoisie, the well off middle-class, the private mansion is the home of the upper class, the wealthier bourgeoisie. (Ledent, 2012). The private mansion, similar to numerous other dwellings of its era, is constructed as a single-family dwelling within the newly established neighbourhoods and alongside the recent constructed avenues. The augmented financial resources of the inhabitant facilitate the erection of larger, more complex, and more ornamented dwellings. Consequently, making a clear distinction within this archetype proves more challenging than with the middle-class townhouse. Nevertheless, an effort was made by the architectural magazine *L'émulation* (La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874) to outline distinctive aspects: among the most notable characteristics (and the primary deviation from the middle-class townhouse) is the width of the dwelling. The width of a private mansion can span up to 10 meters and, in extraordinary circumstances, even more.

Once again, the facade of the private mansion serves as the visage of its occupants to the city. Given the substantial wealth of the owners, these facades are further employed to exhibit their social status. The elements utilized in middle-class townhouses reappear here but in even more decorative forms: vibrant transom windows, stone or cast-iron balustrades, bay windows spanning multiple floors, dormer windows, pillars, imposing pediments, etc. (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). Similarly, there is an abundance of stylistic variation in the treatment of the facade, similar as to the middle-class townhouses. The materials employed range from plastered facades with faux joints to colourful brick patterns and blue or white natural stone. Conversely, little to no attention is paid to the rear facade, which is designed purely for functional purposes, lacking any ornaments.

Figure 1.12: Facade (left) and section (right) of a private mansion (Maton, 2024).

The private mansion comprises three levels (occasionally two), characterised by a ground floor elevation of up to 1 m, notably lower than in the middle-class townhouses (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). Consequently, the basement remains still partially submerged and lighted through a (part of a) street-side window. Furthermore, the private mansion is characterised by the presence of a coach entry on one side of the building. It's common to observe four or five noticeable spans in the facade of such dwellings, as depicted in figure 1.12. Again, this type of dwellings can have a mansard roofs or gable roofs.

Spatial organisation

The wealthy bourgeoisie, more so than the middle class, prefers to keep their staff as invisible as possible. They aim to move away from the traditions of feudal landlords of previous centuries, who displayed their power through the visibility of their servants. The inhabitants' lives are once again considered private and are to be shielded from those unrelated to their affairs (Vandenbreenen & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994). This reinforces the patterns and customs already present in the middle-class townhouse: reception areas and private quarters are further separated, and staff are given entirely separate pathways, which these spacious residences easily accommodate (D'haese, 2012). Naturally, for this class, displaying their social status to guests becomes even more important, resulting in richly decorated and monumental interiors.

The distinction between primary spaces or living areas and secondary spaces reserved for circulation and supporting functions is once again achieved by segmenting the dwelling in multiple longitudinal spans. Perpendicular to the street, a sequence of rooms is arranged in an *enfilade* layout. Like the middle-class townhouse, the dwelling comprises a wider span accommodating the living areas and a narrower span housing the circulation. However, in this archetype, the differentiation between the broader and smaller span becomes less articulated. Additionally, the private mansion features an additional span, the coach entry, where the dwelling's entrance is situated (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). The spatial hierarchy, already evident in middle-class townhouses, is more pronounced in private mansions: the ground floor (or *bel étage*) is exclusively reserved for representative functions, making it the most significant and therefore highest spaces. Spaces facing the street exhibit a more formal character compared to those at the rear. The higher in the dwelling, the more intimate the spaces get, consequently featuring lower ceiling heights. The additional space that is provided by the narrower span, positioned between the broader span and the coach entry, is deployed to make this representative function of the *bel étage* even more eminent.

Figure 1.13: Floor plans of the *bel étage* (left) and first floor (right) level of a private mansion (Maton, 2024).

Despite the variety within this archetype, certain historical sources manage to outline the main features (Cloquet, 1900; Daly, 1864; La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874) which are also identified by more recent literature (D'haese, 2012; Hooft, 1997; Vandenbreenen & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994). Figure 1.13 illustrates this spatial organisation. The private mansion features a coach entry on the periphery of the building, behind which lies a covered passageway. This passage leads to the courtyard at the rear of the dwelling, where various outhouses are located. Central in this covered passageway is the actual entrance to the dwelling through a grand door, adorned with noble materials and pillars. A few (marble) staircases provide transverse access to the *bel étage*, where a large *vestibule* is centrally positioned within the dwelling. Here, a monumental and richly decorated staircase facilitates the circulation of the residents.

Additionally, a service staircase, concealed from the view, often is present in this *vestibule*. This staircase is facilitating the circulation of servants from the basement to the other floors. The *vestibule* is regarded as a neutral zone, the sole area where servants and inhabitants may cross paths. From the *vestibule*, access is provided to the other rooms: a salon at the street side, followed by a dining room, and in some cases, a veranda. These spaces are also equipped with fireplaces for space heating. An additional room is located in the narrow span, which can serve as an office or waiting room. Once again, these spaces are all connected by double swinging doors, enabling secondary circulation.

In the basement, the kitchen is situated alongside various other functional spaces: the laundry room, storage for coal, wine, provisions, etc. It also happens that the kitchen is not placed in the basement, in which case it typically appears on the ground floor at the garden side in the narrow span (an annex was rather uncommon). On upper floors above are the intimate spaces of the residents. The different spaces are accessible from the central *vestibule*. Although intimacy regained importance, it is not uncommon for the wealthy bourgeoisie to have separate bedrooms for the couple, with the man's bedroom facing the street and the woman's facing the garden (following the same hierarchical logic as on the ground floor).

The private mansion distinguishes itself from the middle-class townhouse by its surplus of rooms: in the span above the carriage passageway, we find two additional rooms, and often another extra room is located in the narrower span. Thus, in this archetype, in addition to bedrooms, one often finds a bathroom (or boudoir), a private salon, dressing room, or office on these floors. Once again, the different spaces are interconnected through large double swinging doors, and the main spaces are equipped with fireplaces. The servants' quarters are located in the attic.

Transformations

The transformation of this archetype throughout the recent years are rather scarce. The scale of this dwelling allows a lot of flexibility within the given framework. Naturally, the kitchen in also in these dwellings relocated to the ground floor when originally situated in the basement, and the bathrooms and sanitary facilities are modernised. In some instances, new extensions are added to expand the living areas or incorporate a veranda. Due to the considerable size of the private mansion, they often possess an excess of space for contemporary single-family living. As a result, these properties are frequently repurposed into office buildings or partially converted into student accommodation.

Variants

Similar to the middle-class townhouse, several variants of the private mansion archetype merit distinct attention. The first variant is extensively discussed in *L'émulation* (La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874): the private mansion with a width exceeding 10 meters, representing the most luxurious option for the wealthiest bourgeoisie. This type is exceedingly rare and exhibits significant variation, thus it is considered a variant rather than a separate archetype.

The primary characteristic of this variant is the absence of a coach entry, with the entrance to the residence here positioned along the symmetry axis. Upon entering through the grand front door, one arrives in an *antichambre*, followed by a large *vestibule* dominated by an imposing monumental staircase. The *vestibule* separates the representative rooms (waiting salon, dining room, cloakroom) on one side from the more private representational spaces on the other side (salon, office, library). This type of building is distinguished by an even greater presence of spaces designed to impress guests, such as a ballroom or smoking room located on the first floor. The private quarters of the residents are situated only on the second floor.

Additionally, private mansions situated at the corner of two streets also exist. These mansions have the scale and facade treatment of the archetype, but their internal organisation is once again significantly influenced by the specific context. Analogous to corner houses in middle-class townhouses, the strict hierarchy becomes more fluid, and the distinction between front and back—between front facade and rear facade—becomes less clear. Finally, in the 19th century, private mansions did not typically house commercial spaces. As a result of recent renovations, the ground floor can sometimes accommodate a shop or café nowadays.

1.3.3. Multi-family townhouse

General Description

Although *L'émulation* (La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874), Viollet-Le-Duc (1863), and Daly (1864) clearly distinguish the multi-family townhouse as a separate archetype for Belgium and France, the Ghent professor Cloquet (1900) notes that this type of housing is very rare in the inner city of Ghent. He points out that in cities like Paris or Vienna, a significant number of multi-family townhouses were built in the 19th century, but the Belgian culture is more focused on individual homes for families. Nonetheless, this archetype is considered separately here because large cities like Brussels and Antwerp have a significant presence of this type, particularly from the beginning of the 20th century.

With the rise of the bourgeoisie and thus a more affluent class, housing also became commercialised. This new class aspired to be both property owners and landlords, marking the first time that homeowners were not always the inhabitants (Ledent, 2012). The multi-family townhouses remained a means for the bourgeoisie to display their power and prestige in the city, yet they were intended for the lower bourgeoisie. Co-habitation with multiple families under one roof was long associated with poverty and the working class (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.), thus the truly wealthy population did not reside in this type of dwelling.

The multi-family townhouses were integrated into the urban fabric with the same logic as the middle-class townhouses. They were constructed within the new dense building blocks or along newly developed boulevards, on the same narrow but deep plots. This archetype often resembled a single-family home, with a width typically around 6 meters. Unlike the large-scale rental properties in Paris or Vienna, these apartments were relatively limited in scale. The facade remained significant as a scenery for the city, constructed using similar materials and decorations as the middle-class townhouse, albeit sometimes less luxurious.

The multi-family townhouse typically consisted of 4 or 5 levels, with the ground floor sometimes elevated. Following the same logic as the middle-class townhouse, the ground floor (*bel étage*) could be up to 2 meters above street level. As can be seen in figure 1.14, these buildings were fully underpinned by basements, illuminated by a street-level window if the ground floor is raised. The facade featured 2 or 3 spans, and this type of dwelling could have a gable roof, mansard roof, or flat roof.

Figure 1.14: Facade (left) and section (right) of a multi-family townhouse (Maton, 2024).

Spatial organisation

In contrast to the middle-class townhouse, the multi-family townhouse is organised horizontally rather than vertically, with a different apartment on each floor. In this archetype the logic of the middle-class townhouse is replicated on each level. Likewise, the limited width of the plot but considerable depth results in an *enfilade* of various rooms arranged perpendicularly to the street. Again, there is a division between primary spaces or living areas and secondary spaces by organising the dwelling into two spans. The living areas are situated in the wider span, while the circulation and supporting functions are located in the narrower span. The spatial hierarchy is also applied in the multi-family townhouse, but now only in the horizontal direction: the further towards the garden, the more private the spaces become. The ceiling height of the different levels varies much less as there is no longer a vertical hierarchy, contrary to the previous archetypes. Each floor typically measures between 3 and 4 meters. Nonetheless, it is notable that the ground-floor apartment often has a slightly higher ceiling than the upper apartments. This way, this archetype can still project the image that a 19th-century townhouse aims to present to the city.

The spatial organisation is quite similar to the middle class townhouse, however different sources (Cloquet, 1900; Daly, 1864; La Société Centrale d'Architecture de Belgique, 1874; Vandembreden & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994) highlight the specificities of this archetype (as shown in figure 1.15). Entering the building is identical to the middle-class townhouse: a large door with transom windows leads into the *vestibule* in the narrow span. If there is a raised ground floor, a few (marble) steps bridge the height difference. The *vestibule* serves as a communal space and provides access to the various apartments. At the rear of the *vestibule* is the staircase.

Figure 1.15: Floor plans of the *bel étage* (left) and a higher floor level (right) of a multi-family townhouse (Maton, 2024).

The living areas are located in the broad span, with the most formal space, the salon, positioned at the street side. Behind it are the dining room and, directly behind, the bedroom, the most intimate space. Large double doors are placed between these rooms. The various rooms in the broader bay are equipped with fireplaces for heating. Since each apartment requires its own kitchen, it is located in an extension in the narrow bay, along with the sanitary facilities and occasionally an extra bedroom. This layout is repeated on each floor, with the ground floor sometimes featuring a veranda behind the living spaces.

The basement no longer includes a kitchen, as each floor already has one. The basement is solely used for storage of coal and provisions, and sometimes includes a laundry room. The greater height of these buildings and advancements in technology often result in more vertical utility shafts being present. These shafts are necessary to supply water to the various floors and to provide drainage and ventilation for the toilets.

Variants

The most common variant of the multi-family townhouse is one that includes a commercial space on the ground floor, as described by Vandenbreenen en Dierkens-Aubry (1994). Naturally, such a merchant's house lacks a *bel étage*, as the shop or café must be accessible directly from the street. This typically necessitates two entrances: one for the commercial space on the ground floor and another providing access to the staircase and the residential floors above. The archetypal floor plan, as discussed earlier, is applied here as well, starting from the first floor onwards.

Additionally, multi-family townhouses can also be found on street corners, similar to middle-class townhouses and private mansions. The rigid logic and hierarchy are again complicated by the specific context of the corner location. Providing one apartment per floor appears to be a common solution for addressing the challenges of a corner plot. This configuration frequently coincides with the presence of a shop or café on the ground floor.

1.3.4. Modest house

General Description

During the 19th century, an awareness emerged that the living conditions of workers also required improvement. The densely packed back-to-back houses in enclosed courtyards, combined with poor hygiene and limited access to clean water, led to epidemics and uprisings (Vandenbreenen & Dierkens-Aubry, 1994). Encouraged by municipal and national legislation aimed at ameliorating living conditions, these courtyard houses gradually disappeared from the inner areas of the city blocks in the historical city centres and were relocated to suburban areas on newly developed land (Hooft, 1997).

Towards the end of the 19th century, new laws further promoted the construction and ownership of individual houses for workers, modelled after the bourgeois example (BrusselsRetrofitXL, n.d.). These homes were constructed by the same ruling class that imposed its values and norms on the working class, assuming that everyone should conform to their societal model (Ledent, 2012). They believed that the dwellings of the working class should also contribute to the bourgeois aesthetic of the city. It must be noted that, concurrently, many working-class back-to-back courtyard houses were also constructed in the suburbs, where still little to no attention was given to hygiene or comfort.

Figure 1.16: Facade (left) and section (right) of a modest house (Maton, 2024).

The modest house thus emerged as a reduced version of the middle-class townhouse. These dwellings were built on narrower and shallower plots, often less than 5 meters wide. As illustrated in figure 1.16, modest houses typically consist of two floors, lacking the elevated ground floor characteristic of middle-class townhouses. They were usually finished with mansard roofs and a dormer window. The facades, comprising two bays, were completed with noble materials, albeit less ostentatiously than middle-class townhouses. Exposed brick or plastered facades were complemented by limited ornamentation such as stone sills, a stone base, or coloured brick bands. The back facade is once again of no importance as regards to ornaments.

Spatial organisation

As a reduced version of the middle-class townhouse, the modest house still follows the bourgeoisie organisation but with limited hierarchical principles behind it. The lack of servants in this type of dwelling makes the distinction between reception and service functions redundant (Ledent & Porotto, 2023). However, the house is still divided into two longitudinal spans, with more or less the same width, where one span is dedicated to circulation spaces and the other to living spaces. The spaces facing the street are still considered the most representative, while the higher in the house, the more intimate the functions become. The ceiling heights generally remain consistent, typically not exceeding 3 meters.

Figure 1.17: Floor plans of ground floor (left), first floor (middle) and second floor (right) level of a modest house (Maton, 2024).

The layout of a modest house is thus a simplified version of a bourgeois dwelling, as Louis Cloquet (1900) confirms. Figure 1.17 shows the entry of a modest house through a small hall at the rear of which is a double straight staircase with a landing, providing access to the upper floors. Adjacent to the hall, the bay facing the street contains the salon, with the dining room situated at the back. The *enfilade* typically includes a maximum of two rooms, and in some cases, may be reduced to a single room. An annex behind the staircase houses the kitchen and bathroom, and in exceptional cases, the kitchen is placed in a third room behind the dining room.

The modest house often lacks a basement and, if present, the basement is usually located under the rear section of the house. On the first floor, there are two rooms: a small room at the back and a larger room at the front, both used as bedrooms. The space under the mansards roof is clearly designed to be habited, hence the dormer window. Here more (bed)rooms are located.

Variants

The modest house is a relatively simple type with little variation. While there are always exceptions, such as worker houses with additional floors or an elevated ground floor, this remains one of the most consistent archetypes.

The only variant warranting special attention is the corner house. Instead of the archetypal plan, the various rooms are arranged around the stairwell, reducing the hierarchical distinction between different spaces. The facades, although minimally decorated like those of the other modest houses, make it harder to distinguish between the front and rear facades due to the specific context. Often, there is no longer any contact with the open area in the centre of the city block.

1.4. Case study selection

To obtain an accurate understanding of the occupancy and technical aspects of heritage townhouses, a case study approach is employed in addition to the archetype analysis. This involves comprehensive examinations of selected real-life houses in Ghent. Both long-term measurements (including temperature, relative humidity, CO₂ concentration, etc.) and short-term measurements (such as air tightness, heat flux, etc.) are conducted, supplemented by interviews with the residents. Three townhouses in Ghent have been selected for an in-depth study regarding the long-term measurements. An additional 25 townhouses are listed which can serve as an extension of the researched cases or as a back-up (see Annex A: Interesting case studies Belgium). The following paragraphs provide a brief overview of the three case study buildings, focusing on their heritage value, construction methods and technical installations.

Figure 1.18: Map of Ghent with indication of the case studies and neighbourhoods (Maton, 2024).

1.4.1. Hertstraat

General information

Street:	Hertstraat
Building year:	1914
Surface:	350 m ²
Occupants:	2 adults + 1 adult (duplex apartment)

Architectural information

Archetype:	Middle-class townhouse
Construction type:	Masonry
Level of protection:	Listed as ascertained built heritage with architectural and historical values

Figure 1.19: Facade of Hertstraat (De Jonge, 2024).

Description of the current state

The house in the Hertstraat has two spans, one wide and one narrow, three levels with varying ceiling heights, an underground basement and an attic under the gable roof where a separate duplex apartment is installed. The narrow span of the main building volume is extended with a two-storey annex. The wider span is extended with a one-storey annex. This is a good example of a middle class-townhouse apart from the lack of a semi-underground basement.

The bearing walls and facades are composed of solid brick walls with a thickness varying between 30 and 80 cm. The inner floors are built using wooden beams with a wooden floor on top. The annex, veranda, and back facade were insulated between 1982 and 2000 and finished with a gypsum plaster. The windows in the back facade are a mix of single glazing, older and recent (well performing) double glazing. The front facade is in quasi-original state: the wall is not insulated and finished with a coloured brick pattern. All windows have single glazing (including coloured transoms) except for the windows on the second floor which have double glazing since 1992. The gable roof is insulated and was provided with recent roof windows in 2001.

Figure 1.20: Aerial view of the Hertstraat surroundings (Geopunt, n.d.)

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated through radiators on each floor, but in practice only the ground floor and first floor are heated in the morning and evening hours. In the basement, the gas boiler for central space heating is located. The kitchen and bathrooms have their own separate gas boilers for domestic hot water. On the backwards facing roof photovoltaic panels are placed. The old fireplaces situated in every room of the wider span are still in place but not in use anymore. There is no mechanical ventilation system.

1.4.2. Meersstraat

General information

Street:	Meersstraat
Building year:	1900-1914
Surface:	295 m ²
Occupants:	1 adult, 2 children

Architectural information

Archetype:	Middle-class townhouse
Construction type:	Masonry
Level of protection:	Not listed nor protected. Located in the buffer zone around the UNESCO world heritage site of the Belfry.

Figure 1.21: Facade of Meersstraat (De Block et al., 2024).

Description of the current state

The house in the Meersstraat has two spans, one wide and one narrow, three levels with varying ceiling heights, a basement and an attic under the gable roof. This is a good example of a 19th century middle class-townhouse. The ground floor (*bel étage*) is raised about 150 cm to provide the basement with daylight. Here, the actual living rooms can be found which give access to the garden through a (more recent) veranda. On the *bel étage* and first floor, the bedrooms and bathrooms are situated.

The bearing walls and facades are composed of solid brick walls with a thickness varying between 30 and 80 cm. The inner floors are built using wooden beams with a wooden floor on top. The front facade of the house is barely modified: the wooden windows on the first and second floor are still original and are equipped with single glazing. The white plastered facade with natural stone plinth is still in original state, and thus without insulation. The other windows are retrofitted with double glazing in 2000. At the same time, the back wall was retrofitted with 10 cm of cellular glass insulation. Also in 2000, the roof was insulated and retrofitted with new roof windows.

Figure 1.22: Aerial view of the Meersstraat surroundings (Geopunt, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated through radiators on each floor, but in practice only the basement and *bel étage* are heated in the morning and evening hours. This central space heating is provided by a gas boiler. The kitchen and bathroom have their own separate boilers for domestic hot water, an electric one in the kitchen and a gas-based boiler in the bathroom. The old fireplaces situated in every room of the wider span are still in place but not in use anymore. There is no mechanical ventilation system, with exception of a local extraction fan in the bathroom.

1.4.3. Hoogstraat

General information

Street:	Hoogstraat
Building year:	1830-1850
Surface:	900 m ²
Occupants:	1 adult

Architectural information

Archetype:	Private mansion
Construction type:	Masonry
Level of protection:	Protected cityscape with historic and socio-cultural values and listed as ascertained built heritage with architectural and historical values

Figure 1.23: Facade of Hoogstraat (Google, n.d.-b)

Description of the current state

The house in the Hoogstraat is good illustration of a private mansion, with four spans and three levels, each with varying ceiling heights. The ground floor (*bel étage*) is raised 1 m to provide the basement with daylight. Today, the living spaces are located at the rear of the basement, with direct access to the garden. Transverse to the coach entry an elaborately decorated hallway gives access to the *bel étage* and first floor. The second floor and attic are reached through an adjacent staircase. On the *bel étage* additional salons are provided, on the upper floors storage, ateliers and bedrooms.

The bearing walls and facades are composed of solid brick walls with a thickness varying between 30 and 80 cm. The inner floors are built using wooden beams with a wooden floor on top. Almost the entire house is still in its original shape: the wooden windows and are still original and single-glazed. Neither of the facades have been retrofitted, and the interior has been preserved. Only the basement is renovated and equipped with new double-glazed windows.

Figure 1.24: Aerial view of the Hoogstraat surroundings (Geopunt, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated through floor heating in the basement and on the *bel étage* (where the heating system is placed against the ceiling of the basement). The original (and less efficient) radiators are still present in most of the rooms, where it covers the peak heating demand. In practice, only the living spaces in the basement and on the *bel étage* are heated. A gas boiler is providing water at higher and lower temperature, both for space heating and domestic hot water. The old fireplaces situated in every living space are still in place but not in use anymore. The house is ventilated naturally, with the supply air preheated or -cooled by a pipe in the ground. There are photovoltaic panels on the south facing roof.

2. Norway

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2.1. Relevance of studied typology

In Norway, the studied typology is the massive wood (*laftevegg* and *reisverk*) heritage townhouse from the period 1800-1945. The case area neighbourhood in Bakklandet, Trondheim (see figure 2.1), represents a relatively large area of a cultural heritage environment, consisting of detached and semi-detached houses. In Norway, these building types represent 71% of the total historical residential building stock dated up to 1945, and 11% of the total residential building stock until 2021 (Statistics Norway, 2024).

Figure 2.1: Typical street-view in the cultural heritage environment at Bakklandet neighbourhood (Flyen, 2024h).

Only in Japan (Christensen, 1999), more wooden log buildings have been preserved from before the reformation (1536 CE) than in Norway (Berg, 1997). In Europe, outside Scandinavia, there are barely traces of wooden log buildings older than 1500 CE. Within Scandinavia, it is mainly in Norway such houses are preserved (Berg, 1998; Hauglid, 1980).

Wooden log buildings appear in the Alps, the Eastern European mountain-areas, Russian forest areas and in the Nordic countries, roughly corresponding to the extent of coniferous forests (Christie, 1974). The occurrence of wooden log buildings was probably more common when the coniferous forests were larger in extent, but there are few archaeological traces (ibid). Traces of wooden log buildings from around year 0 CE have however been found (ibid). In Scandinavia, wooden log buildings developed around the Viking Age (approximately 700 - 1050 CE) (Christie, 1974).

The Nordic Wooden Town and wooden residential buildings are found at several locations in Northern Europe (Kalakoski et al., 2019). Examples in Norway cover, in addition to Trondheim, the cities of Bergen and Røros (on the UNESCO world heritage list), Grimstad, Kristiansand, Laerdal, Lillehammer, Lillesand, Oslo, Skudeneshavn, Stavanger, Risør, and more. There are also several smaller wooden building environments with high heritage value in semi-urban and rural areas all over the country. The use of wood as the main material in constructions is deeply rooted in Nordic building traditions and practices (Drange et al., 2011; Grytli, 2004). Kalakoski et al. (2019) maintain how timber has been the prevailing building construction material in the Nordic countries until early 20th century. Until 1900, most Norwegian residential buildings were wooden log constructions (Grytli, 2004). In smaller domestic buildings, wood is still the preferred material for both main constructions, claddings etc., however the construction techniques are mostly wooden framework and massive wood constructions (Abed et al., 2022; Harte, 2017; Friedly, 2002). Although tall-raised buildings have not traditionally been built until the 20th century, and then mainly in steel and concrete, massive wood constructions are becoming increasingly more common also in tall building constructions (Mohammadi & Ling, 2017). This is mainly due to carbon storage and sustainable properties (Abed et al., 2022). The continuous and living use of wood as a construction material manifests the continuous importance and vitality of wooden practices and emphasizes the necessity of developing and disseminating knowledge of historic practices and present relevance.

The Nordic wooden towns are recognized as important heritage phenomena with regional origin in Fennoscandia (Kalakoski et al., 2019). Fennoscandia is defined as the geographic area covering Norway, Sweden, Finland, the Cola Peninsula and Russian Karelia, with similarities in i.a. culture and building traditions (Kalakoski et al., 2019). Being listed in the UNESCO World Heritage List, the wooden towns of Old Rauma in Finland and Røros in Norway are recognized as important cultural heritage environments at a global level (UNESCO, 2024).

Many of these wooden heritage environments are, and have been for decades, threatened by challenges such as decay, lack of maintenance, unsuccessful energy efficiency measures, urban development pressure, and changed user requirements (see for instance Kosonen & Keskiisaari, 2020; Flyen et al., 2019; Godbolt et al., 2018; Flyen et al., 2018). The wooden heritage environments are presently threatened by increasing climate strain mainly due to increasing temperatures, precipitation, and following increasing rot decay risk (Fufa et al., 2020). However, the wooden heritage also represents an important resource in terms of potential climate change mitigation compared with demolishing and building new, even before considering the heritage value aspects (Fufa et al., 2021; Flyen et al., 2020). Abed et al. (2022) emphasize how some of many benefits of timber is being a renewable building material that not only reduces emissions but creates negative emissions through carbon storage. In developing wooden heritage buildings to becoming more energy efficient and sustainable through upgrading solutions attending to heritage values, the life cycle of the buildings is in addition prolonged.

2.1.1. Potential risk of wood decay in Norway

Weather and climate in Norway are characterized by large regional and local variations. In the coastal areas the climate is maritime, warm and humid, and with small diurnal, seasonal, and annual fluctuations. The East and central parts of Norway have a continental climate with large temperature fluctuations and low precipitation. Precipitation and temperature are the two basic elements for fungi growth on wood constructions and development of wood decay. Since future scenarios of Norwegian climate show an increase of both temperatures and precipitation, especially on the western coasts, the risk of wood decay will increase considerably. In the Norwegian context, potential decay in wood structures above ground is divided in low, medium and high risk. Scheffer (1971) developed a calculation method to 'yield an index of the relative potential of a climate to promote decay of off-the-ground wood structures' in the US. This method was later adapted to the Norwegian context by Lisø et.al. (2006). The resulting climate index consists of a temperature and a humidity factor which are at the basis of the potential development of wood decay due to fungal attack. The index ranges from 1 to 100 and is divided in thirds to get low, medium and high potential risk, as follows: low decay risk equals to or less than 24, medium decay risk equals to the range 25 - 48, and high decay risk equals to values above 48.

According to the historical records of annual precipitations measured in the period 1971-2000, the largest annual precipitations occurred along the west coast and the highest annual temperatures occurred in the South coastal areas. The resulting climate index and risk of wood decay is calculated to range between 1 and 73 and shown in Figure 2.2: Risk of wood decay in historic normal period 1971-2000, in Norway (Tilley Tajet & Hygen, 2017).figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Risk of wood decay in historic normal period 1971-2000, in Norway (Tilley Tajet & Hygen, 2017).

The future climate scenarios for Norway are derived according to the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP), which describe future scenarios for greenhouse gas emissions, derived from data of the IPCC 5th assessment report (IPCC, 2013). Two scenarios are used, RCP4.5 describes a world with increasing emissions to the mid-century and thereafter reductions, whereas RCP8.5 describes a world with continuous increase of climate gas emission, a business-as-usual scenario. The maps in figure 2.3 show the risk of wood decay in Norway, and are based on the resulting average of 9 climate models developed according to either RCPs and for two time-horizons: the period 2031-2060, and 2071-2100. The potential risk of wood decay is clearly expanding in the two different periods and for both future scenarios. High risk of wood decay extends around the coastline and expanding further inland Norway and further north. This is not surprising since the scenarios show warmer climate and more precipitation in the future. The development in Norway from the historic grid to two future periods shows that high risk of wood decay is expanding into continental parts of Norway inland from the coastal areas. By the end of the century low risk of wood decay is expected to be limited to mountain areas in South Norway and some areas in northern Norway only. Given the expected future high risk of damage and eventual loss of wooden structures, the choice of focussing on historical wooden townhouses derives from the likely high risk of damage and loss of historical value that may occur due to increased weather impact. In addition to the increasing weather impact, the implementation of energy retrofitting solutions that do not consider attentively the problem of water build-up in historical wooden structure, will exacerbate the risk of wood decay, as explained in the following chapters.

Figure 2.3: Risk of wood decay in scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for future period until 2100. (Tilley Tajet & Hygen, 2017)

2.2. Neighbourhood selection

The city of Trondheim, in Trøndelag county, has a long and rich history with a range of cultural heritage environments kept. These environments are emphasized as an important premise for further urban development (Trondheim municipality, 2024a). The municipality have been focusing on safeguarding the municipality's cultural heritage since the 1970s. Following a resolution in the city council in 2013, a dedicated map displaying selected cultural environments and buildings classified in antiquarian/heritage value classes A, B and C was developed. The mapped cultural environments mainly comprise groups of culturally historically valuable buildings and the green landscape around them. New consideration zones are primarily linked to the adopted urban development strategy for Trondheim, and mark where cultural environments can be included as a resource when new areas are to be densified. It has been important that the consideration zones represent a large breadth of the city's history, and from different time periods (Trondheim municipality, 2024b).

The main city core of Trondheim, Midtbyen, is surrounded by the river Nidelven to the West, South, and East, and facing a sea-water canal towards the North (see figure 2.4, left). The neighbourhood Bakklandet is situated on the East bank of the river (see figure 2.4, right). Bakklandet was Trondheim's first suburb, emerged in the mid-1600s. During the Swedish siege of the city in 1658, all the buildings were burned down and then later rebuilt. In 1718, the neighbourhood was once again set on fire, this time by Norwegian forces as a defensive measure against Swedish troops during the Great Nordic War (between 1700 and 1721), and again rebuilt (Bratberg, 2008).

Figure 2.4: Map displaying the city core of Trondheim, surrounded by the river Nidelven, with Bakklandet neighbourhood highlighted in green (left). The selected neighbourhood Bakklandet, highlighted in yellow, is situated on the East bank of the river Nidelv, with the main city core on the West bank (right) (SINTEF, 2024).

Bakklandet neighbourhood is a district within the main core of Trondheim where people live, work, and interact. It is characterized by shared physical features, social connections, and a sense of community, due to the uniformity of the small, two-storey wooden residential buildings that characterize the street fronts. The neighbourhood has a specific unity within the urban fabric due to its own character, amenities, and identity. The individual houses and buildings contribute to the overall character and functionality of the neighbourhood (see figure 2.5-2.7). This is physically shown by larger wooden warehouses towards the riverbank, narrow cobblestone alleys, and two to three storey low-ceiling wooden buildings on the back side along the main streets that crosses the whole neighbourhood: Øvre Bakklandet from south, and Nedre Bakklandet and Nygata from north. Øvre Bakklandet and Nedre Bakklandet meet at the crossing that leads, through the old city bridge Bybrua, to the city centre and the Nidaros cathedral. The wooden town houses that characterize the neighbourhood are often occupied by commercial activities at the ground floor, and residential use at the first and attic floors. This is especially visible in the buildings closer to the Bybrua, where the 'centre' of Bakklandet can be identified. Commercial and residential use is present in the warehouses that face the Nidelva river (as shown in figure 2.6).

The presence of mixed use buildings in Bakklandet can be traced back to its foundation, since the residents were mainly small traders, craftsmen, and labourers. The houses were simple, often single-story structures. Some merchants who owned city-side breweries also established warehouses on Bakklandet due to restrictions on storing flammable products in the city's breweries (Bratberg, 2008). The buildings, dating back to the 1700s, were predominantly crafted from timber. These modest structures reflect the practicality and resourcefulness of the working class. The small, unpretentious dwellings were home to labourers, artisans, and their families. Their modest size and simple design reflect the financial limitations faced by these working-class individuals. Despite their simplicity, they have endured through the centuries, bearing witness to the lives of those who inhabited them. The tightly packed arrangement of buildings along the winding streets of Bakklandet mirrors the close-knit community that once thrived there. These houses stood side by side, forming a cohesive fabric of daily life. The proximity of homes to each other fostered social bonds and a sense of shared experience among the residents. The local architecture tells a story of economic struggle.

In 1846, Bakklandet was incorporated in the city of Trondheim (Bratberg, 2008). The introduction of building restrictions in 1845 led to the decline of wooden structures in the central city area. Over time, the buildings were neglected and deteriorated. Despite this, many of them continued to be used as homes, but various restorations have compromised their authenticity. The uncertainty surrounding Bakklandet's future, linked to plans for large-scale demolition due to a proposed main road through the area, led property owners to neglect the maintenance of the buildings. However, the neighbourhood experienced a revival when the plans for the main road were abandoned, demonstrating how thoughtful preservation can enhance the appeal of a neglected historic residential area (Bratberg, 2008). In the 1960s, the buildings in the area were threatened to be demolished. From the late 1970s, the neighbourhood underwent significant changes, transitioning from a worn-down, industrial area to a highly attractive residential and partly commercial district. Renovated houses presently coexist with a vibrant social scene, including numerous restaurants, cafes, and small shops (Bratberg, 2008).

Figure 2.5: Typical view in the narrow streets of Baklandet, in the small-scale, two to three storey wooden log buildings (Flyen, 2024i).

Figure 2.6: Industrial warehouses on both sides of the river Nidelven. Baklandet to the right, have similar facades, as seen here on the West bank and the city core side of the river (left in the picture) (Flyen, 2022).

Figure 2.7: Bakklandet heritage environment is characterized by a variety of culture heritage buildings with different heritage values and use, although most buildings are within the archetype wooden log townhouse. The yellow building to the left is protected according to the Cultural Heritage Act (Kulturminneloven, 2018, §§ 15-21) (Flyen, 2024a).

The individual buildings in Bakklandet hold significant cultural heritage value by documenting the history of the area and of Trondheim. A few have even been protected according to the Cultural Heritage Act (Kulturminneloven, 2018, §§ 15-21). It is however the holistic, entirety of the area that emerges as the most important cultural heritage asset (see figure 2.7), given by the large and cohesive environment formed by the buildings. Despite alterations and restorations over time, the small-scale character of the structures remains preserved.

Cultural heritage and historic environments play a crucial role in shaping the identity, and serve as rich source of knowledge, experiences, and economic value. By preserving, respecting and developing cultural and heritage values, the identity of local communities is strengthened. Many cultural heritage sites have significant practical resources, as these historic environments serve modern and future populations, providing recreational spaces for residents and tourist, and enhancing overall quality of life, which become more relevant as urban density increases. Bakklandet, as one of Trondheim's most well-defined older neighbourhoods, exemplifies the cultural history of the working class and labour. This area, rejuvenated by younger generations through house renovations, significantly contribute to the city's character. Beyond creating a sense of place, the cultural heritage also has practical value. The existing building stock represents substantial resources, both economically and environmentally (Trondheim municipality, 2024a). Variety in size and architectural styles tells the story of the city. Small-scale businesses, like those on Bakklandet, contribute to vibrant urban life. Recognizing the climate impact, preserving cultural heritage remains central to urban development. Not only individual buildings but also situations where multiple structures and landscapes form cohesive environments must be considered (see figure 2.8).

Today, Bakklandet is a lively residential neighborhood, bustling with life. Its picturesque streets and charming buildings, adorned with small restaurants, bars, and shops, attract both locals and tourists alike, and showcases a range of valuable aspects. The chosen neighbourhood holds high historical value as a prime example of a working-class suburb constructed primarily from timber. Its small, closely clustered buildings lining the narrow streets serve as tangible symbols of the economic conditions faced by labourers during their time (Bratberg, 2008). In conclusion, Bakklandet’s heritage values lie not only in its architectural features but also in the collective memory of the working-class lives that unfolded in the neighbourhood. It stands as a reminder of the human stories embedded in the built environment, connecting us to the past and enriching our understanding of history.

Figure 2.8: Mixed-purpose map, displaying a section of the Cultural Heritage map super-imposed on a map of the city core of Trondheim. Bakklandet is the area within the red stripe/boundary to the right in the picture, on the East riverbank. The map gives an indication of a complex cultural heritage environment, with a high density of valuable heritage buildings and environments. Buildings in red are protected/listed, purple buildings are considered of high heritage value and blue buildings are considered of antiquarian value (Trondheim municipality, 2024b).

2.3. Archetype selection

The main characteristics that define the archetype of the historical Norwegian townhouses can be summarized into the buildings' appearance and their massive wood construction systems. The selection of the archetype is therefore based on those townhouses of Bakklandet that complies with these two characteristics. This chapter gives an overview of the archetype and their architectural characteristics, and details of their construction systems.

2.3.1. History of wood construction in Norway

Until around 1900, most wooden dwellings in Norway were built with wood log constructions (*laftevegg*). The wood log construction consists of logs of which ends are shaped in either 'tongue' or 'groove'. The logs are laid on top of each other and joined by the ending tongue-and-grooves at the corners. To make the construction stable, the joints between the logs must be as tight as possible, and dowels are used to prevent the logs from twisting or slipping. Dowels are wooden pegs that are hammered to connect adjacent logs, they are often placed at about 3 meters and never above each other. The joints between the logs were sealed with moss. Initially, the log constructions were left exposed, but, as sawing techniques were developed and mechanized during the 18th and 19th centuries, it became common to finish the walls externally and partly internally with cladding panels. Since the cladding gave the houses a refined look and larger possibilities for architectural expressions, its use became common from 1900, when a windproof layer made of lining paper was also introduced next to the cladding layer.

Figure 2.9: Section of a Norwegian wood log construction (*laftevegg*) with external cladding (left), and image of similar construction left exposed (right) (Grytli, 2004).

FIG 2. Different corner notches of the log wall: double notch with wind lock (1), Scandinavian saddle notch (also known as Norwegian notch) (2), dovetail notch (3) and corner post (4).

Figure 2.10: Examples corner joints of wood log constructions (Alev et al., 2014).

The market development of houses with cladding finishing was facilitated by the introduction of an alternative structural system. The wood log construction was replaced by a timber frame construction with posts and sleepers and an infill of vertically aligned wood planks (*reisverk*). The planks are often 7" x 3" and fastened together with dowels. Tongue-and-groove planks are or in some cases loose planks. This type of wood construction was initially used in the second half of the 1700 when the infill of the timber frame was constituted by non-load-bearing wood posts. From 1850 onwards this system was further developed into a material-saving construction by replacing the wood posts with wood planks in the timber frame infilling. The use of such a type of timber frame structure (*reisverk*) gives the advantage of a lower shrinkage of the wood elements compared to that happening in the log construction (*laftevegg*), because the wood posts have a significantly shorter length than that of the wood logs. This meant that the once the structural system of the house was complete, the finishing with cladding, details, and furnishing could be set in place in quite a short time, compared to that of a log house. On the other hand, the *reisverk* construction was more prone to becoming drafty, because the wooden planks were not pressed together when they shrunk during the drying process, as it was happening for the wood logs. Hence the use of a wind barrier in the form of lining paper to be placed just behind the external cladding.

Figure 2.11: Scheme of *reisverk* constructions (Byggforskserien, 2017).

2.3.2. Wooden log townhouse

An archetype in the context of buildings refers to a fundamental, universally recognizable pattern or template that embodies specific qualities or characteristics. These archetypal building forms transcend time, culture, and geographical boundaries. Architects and designers draw upon these archetypes to create structures that resonate with human experiences and evoke a sense of familiarity. Building archetypes emerge from humanity's collective memory and shared experiences. They represent essential forms that recur across different architectural styles and historical periods. These patterns are deeply ingrained in our cultural consciousness.

Wood has been a primary building material in Norway for centuries. Traditional wooden cabins, farmhouses, and coastal cottages showcase the country's affinity for wood. These structures blend seamlessly with the natural landscape and reflect Norway's architectural heritage.

Figure 2.12: Typical feature of the archetype Wooden log townhouse, in Baklandet (Flyen, 2024g).

The chosen archetype for this project is timber/wooden log town houses. Although the number of traditional log buildings in Norway is not extensive, they hold significant cultural value. Adapting these structures for modern comfort without compromising their heritage value is challenging. Introducing new materials for insulation and density must be done carefully to avoid damaging the buildings, including the construction, the wood, and the indoor climate. Knowledge about upgrading these buildings is valuable for preservation. Therefore, selecting timber/wooden log townhouses as an archetype is essential.

The primary structure is made of massive wood, featuring either a wood log system or a system composed by vertical wooden planks within a timber frame. More details of these two construction systems are described in the following chapters.

Main features of the archetype include:

- Main construction is massive wood;
- Panelled facades, at least towards the main street;
- Small-paned windows;
- Mainly residential, some commercial activities on the main floor;
- One to two (sometimes three) floors; attic under the roof;
- Normally saddle/gable roof;
- Location: directly passage from the street, often with a small backyard and/or outhouse;
- Originally heated by open fireplace and/or wood stove;
- Dense housing, the townhouses are positioned very close, shoulder-by-shoulder (see figure 2.12).

2.3.3. Typical failures in historical wood constructions

Wood log constructions (laftevegg)

Since the facades are exposed to the weather, most of the occurring damage is caused by water, such as rain, roof leaks, defective gutters/drains, water drawn up from the ground, and water from a humid indoor climate. Damage occurs also due to water being collected in the wood structure after a very thick layer of paint is laid on the indoor and outdoor surfaced of the wood logs, which prevents the humidity in the wood elements from escaping, and thus from letting the structure to dry. Similarly to paints, the use of too dense wood surface treatments causes to trap water inside the structure and consequentially rot damage. Additional insulation placed on the indoor side of the facade causes the wall to become colder and less permeable to air. The water accumulating in the wood elements has limited possibility to escape thus increasing the risk of rot damage.

When a cladding layer has been added to finish the construction and insulation is blown into the cavity between the cladding and the wall, rot damage is very likely to occur due to the same mechanism of limiting the accumulating water escaping the structure. If the insulation is added to the indoor side of the construction, the construction becomes colder and slower to dry in mid-seasons.

Timber frame construction (reisverk)

This timber frame construction consists of layers of wood panels wrapped on both the indoor and outdoor sides by lining paper or cardboard functioning as a wind barrier. The lining paper provide a good airtightness however, air leakages are often happening at typical weak points of the structure, such as joints/sealing around windows and other wall openings, as well as the transition to the floor/foundation and to the roof or floor partition. The air leakage of the construction is beneficial for any potentially trapped water to escape, and thus limiting the risk of water buildup and rotting. This positive characteristic of the timber frame/*reisverk* construction still holds when an external cladding is applied without a properly ventilated gap between the cladding and the frame construction. On the other hand, because of its characteristics, such timber frame construction does not provide adequate insulated levels according to today's requirements. To increase the wall's insulation capacities by blowing insulation into cavities is thus sometimes performed. However, this reduces the drying characteristics of the construction and allows for water to build-up. The retrofitting of such constructions with additional insulation and sealing, including the replacement of windows/sealing around windows, requires improvements to the ventilation system, e.g. by installing wall vents in all rooms (natural ventilation) and/or mechanical ventilation to maintain a good performance of the structure.

2.4. Case study selection

The selection of the case studies is made by identifying those townhouses in Baklandet that features the characteristics defined in the above archetype section. A list of potential candidates was drawn based on the availability of documentation in historical archives and in the archive of building properties, and on the availability of the owners to participate in the activities of Heritace. Some of the case studies are used for commercial activities and other are residential only. It was decided to have a representation of commercial activities and residential buildings in the selection since their different use lead to the occurrence of different problems, especially in relation to the moisture production load and its effect on the wood structure. Moreover, the different patterns of occupancy and energy use between residential and commercial buildings, lead to different strategies for energy retrofitting, which are worth being investigated. Figure 2.14 shows the 8 candidates for being case studies, of which a smaller sample will be selected for further studies. Most of the buildings are characterised by a living area (kitchen, rooms) surrounded by storage rooms, technical spaces, and an open courtyard, to which it is accessed by a roofed but open passage. In some buildings, the living area is clearly defined by a vaguely regular rectangular floor plan, to which storage rooms are encroached within the border of the plot. In other buildings, a clear definition between the living area and the storage and technical space is not present.

Figure 2.13: Map of Trondheim with the Baklandet area highlighted in green. A total of 8 buildings are under consideration as case studies (highlighted in black) (SINTEF, 2024).

Figure 2.14: Overview of the 8 buildings that are under consideration as cases (Flyen, 2024f).

Table 2.1 below presents the buildings shortlisted and prioritized for potential inclusion as case study objects in the Bakklundet case study area, within the categories *Not Intervened*, *Bad/Some intervention*, *Good intervention*, and *Listed building* (seen from a cultural heritage point of view). Three building owners have agreed to include their house as a case in the project. All eight buildings on the shortlist (table 2.1) are within the archetype of timber/wooden log buildings, built in different years within the chosen time frame and with different heritage values and cultural heritage statuses. They will be employed in the qualitative interviews/survey at neighbourhood and individual levels.

Category	Priority	Address
<i>Not Intervened</i>	1.	Nygata/a: High antiquarian value
<i>Not Intervened</i>	2.	Nedre Bakklundet/b: High antiquarian value
<i>Not Intervened, planned total renovation</i>	3.	Nedre Bakklundet/c: High antiquarian value
<i>Bad/Some Intervention</i>	1.	Nedre Bakklundet/d: Antiquarian value
<i>Bad/Some Intervention</i>	2.	Nedre Bakklundet/e: Antiquarian value
<i>Good Intervention</i>	1.	Nedre Bakklundet/f: Very high antiquarian value
<i>Listed Building</i>	1.	Øvre Bakklundet/g: Protected
<i>Listed Building</i>	2.	Nedre Bakklundet/h: High antiquarian value

Table 2.1: Overview of the buildings prioritized for inclusion as case study objects in the Bakklundet case study area, distributed into categories according to level of intervention

2.4.1. Nygata

General information

Street:	Nygata
Building year:	Before 1900 (SEFRAK registered)
Surface:	86.3 m ² (property area)
Occupants:	Residential

Architectural information

Archetype:	Wooden log town house
Construction type:	Massive wood/wooden log
Level of protection:	Registered of high heritage value, without legal protection

Figure 2.15: Facade of Nygata, Trondheim (Flyen, 2024d).

Description of the current state

Not a lot of interventions have been introduced. The building is worn down and is probably not well maintained, based on visual inspection of the outside. The windows are from the 1950s. The Municipal Cultural Heritage authorities indicate that they are likely to accept quite extensive renovation of windows if applied for. In terms of authenticity, the construction seems to be quite close to the original. The owner has agreed to be included in the project.

The lack of adequate financial subsidy schemes that encourage energy upgrading of private homes is perceived as a barrier for owners of residents like this.

Description of the technical equipment

The heat generation system is probably mainly electric heating but might include one or more wood-burning stoves in addition. There are not likely any cooling and/or ventilation systems, PV systems, or similar. Present situation will be investigated in the field study.

Figure 2.16: Facade of Nygata and neighbouring environment, Trondheim (Flyen, 2024c).

2.4.2. Nedre Bakklandet

General information

Street:	Nedre Bakklandet
Building year:	Before 1900 (SEFRAK registered)
Surface:	261 m ² (property area)
Occupants:	Residential

Architectural information

Archetype:	Wooden log townhouse
Construction type:	Massive wood/wooden log
Level of protection:	Registered of heritage value, without legal protection

Figure 2.17: Facade of Nedre Bakklandet, Trondheim (Flyen, 2024b).

Description of the current state

The building's cladding is original; however some new elements (windows) have been introduced in the building. The construction is close to the original. One of the apartments owners has agreed to be included in the project.

Description of the technical equipment

The heat generation system is probably mainly electric heating but might include one or more wood-burning stoves in addition. There are not likely any cooling and/or ventilation systems, PV systems, or similar. Present situation of the installed technical equipment will be evaluated in the field study.

2.4.1. Øvre Bakklandet

General information

Street:	Øvre Bakklandet
Building year:	Before 1900 (SEFRAK registered)
Surface:	231 m ² (property area)
Occupants:	Commercial (restaurant)

Architectural information

Archetype:	Wooden log town house
Construction type:	Massive wood/wooden log
Level of protection:	Registered of high heritage value, with legal protection

Figure 2.18: Facade of Øvre Bakklandet, Trondheim (Flyen, 2024e).

Description of the current state

The building has many original elements (cladding, windows, wood log structure) and it is protected. It is currently used as a restaurant.

Description of the technical equipment

The heat generation system is probably mainly electric heating but might also include one or more wood-burning stoves in addition. An industrial kitchen is present, plus ventilation system in the kitchen. There are not likely any cooling and/or ventilation systems in the dining area, PV systems or similar. Present situation of the installed technical equipment will be evaluated in the field study.

3. Estonia

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3.1. Relevance of studied typology

In Estonia, wood has been the main traditional building material over centuries. Most of the remaining wooden apartment buildings that originate from the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century are forming well-preserved entities (Arumägi, 2015). This is also the era when architecture began to be commissioned by Estonian society and was designed for this society by Estonian architects (Arumägi, 2015).

Large-scale urban areas of wooden apartment buildings, that are still preserved in Tallinn, Tartu, or other cities and towns in Estonia, tend to be quite rare in the cities of Europe.

Wooden apartment buildings cover ca 5% of the whole building stock net area and over 50% of the building stock built before 1945. Masonry heritage apartment buildings predating 1945 in Estonia, with case-studies in Tallinn, make up to approximately 1% of whole building stock net area. In addition, many masonry apartment buildings built between 1945 and 1955 (Stalinist style) are either protected as a national monument, located in a heritage conservation area or situated in a milieu valuable area.

3.2. Neighbourhood selection

In many towns in Estonia well-preserved areas were built mainly before the Second World War (WWII) and are listed as milieu valuable areas, meaning the coherent historical housing environment as assessed by planning experts. Not all the buildings in the building environment are formally listed. Even so, these buildings constitute an important part of the built heritage and are subject to demands set by different regulations, such as energy efficiency on one hand and the heritage regulations on the other hand. It is important to understand that historic buildings need a protection from unsuitable retrofit measures and the character of urban area must be preserved (Arumägi, 2015). Preserving early wooden districts is essential because they represent an important stage in the history of the development of Tallinn.

Tallinn enacted eight milieu protection areas in 2001. Today there are altogether 78 milieu valuable areas in Estonia. Such areas encompass cultural and historical as well as social values, and their preservation is important from both the cultural point of view and that of national and local identity (Arumägi, 2015). The buildings are graded as highly valuable, valuable, milieu valuable and low-value buildings in addition to officially listed cultural monuments that can also be situated in milieu valuable areas (Arumägi, 2015).

In addition to a single building, also a district can be valuable for its distinctive character. Important elements that express the character are defined mainly as an urban pattern, the formal appearance of buildings (both interior and exterior, defined by scale, size, style, construction, material, colour and decoration) but also the various functions the area has acquired over the time (Arumägi, 2015).

The area of milieu value of Uue-Maailma (New World) used to be a meadow until the middle of 19th century. Most of the wooden apartment buildings were built between 1890 and 1939, and brick apartment buildings in the 1950–60s. The residential area in the proximity of Luther Plywood and Furniture Factory (founded in 1883) began to develop due to the need for accommodation for the workers. The first houses were two-story, wooden apartment buildings called the Lender's building. The construction of new buildings in Uue-Maailma was resumed after the end of the First World War (WWI) in 1923, when they continued to build wooden apartment buildings, this time two- to three-story houses with brick stairwells called the Tallinn building. In areas where buildings were destroyed in the WWII bombings in 1944, new ones were built later. Those are massive brick apartment buildings from the Stalinist-era in the 1950s, positioned as an ensemble. In the 1960s and 1970s, some industrially designed brick and/or panel apartment buildings were constructed. Thus, the development of this area that is now considered of milieu value consists of a variety of building types of different size and construction materials allowing to follow and retell the historical events that have formed Tallinn.

Figure 3.1: The area of Uue-Maailma on a map of Tallinn (left) (Tallinna Linnaplaneerimise Amet, 2017) and the milieu-valuable area of Uus-Maailm (right) (Tallinn, n.d.).

3.3. Archetype selection

3.3.1. Wooden apartments of 'Lender' type

One of the most typical wooden apartment buildings in Tallinn is referred to as the 'Lender's' building type. There are about a thousand of them still preserved (Martin, 2014).

The type is named after Voldemar Lender, the engineer that initially started to design them and later (1906-1913) became the first Estonian nationality mayor of the capital Tallinn. The type originates from the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century and was designed for poor Estonian nationality peasants who came from the countryside to work in various industrial sights and could only afford to rent an inexpensive apartment.

The Lender's buildings typically have two floors, are symmetrical and made of limestone (foundation and plinth) and horizontal logs. The facade is covered with horizontal boarding, some are more decorative and others very simple, the front door being the only aesthetically designed element. The roof type is open gable.

Figure 3.2: What the earliest Lender's building was designed to look like (Õle 42, Tallinn) (Martin, 2014, p. 4).

Figure 3.3: The building was usually constructed much less detailed or lost its finesse during various reconstructions (Õle 42, Tallinn) (Martin, 2014, p. 4).

Figure 3.4: The original floorplan (Õle 42, Tallinn) (Martin, 2014, p. 4).

The main facade is facing the street, contrary to earlier buildings, and the front door is in the middle of the facade. The central axis is also highlighted with the awning above the door and raised roof for a small attic window. Originally these buildings had only one wooden stairwell but due to the change in fire safety regulations they later had to add the second (the same regulations also lead to the design of so-called Tallinn buildings that have one brick stairwell, see below).

Early Lender's buildings had four or eight apartments that consisted of only one room each. Apartments were positioned on both sides of the central corridor (oriented across the building from front to back). Corridors initially also served as shared kitchens, later when the second stairway or additional stairwell was added, the stoves were moved inside the apartments. Dry toilets were in a separate building in the courtyard or later constructed in the back stairwell or added in the corridors. Nevertheless, those were considered somewhat modern amenities compared to the living conditions in smaller towns and rural areas where the workers came from.

Figure 3.5: The floorplan of early Lender's building. 1 - entrance hall, 2 - kitchen-corridor, 3 - living rooms/apartments (Uukado, 2024, p. 66).

There are several subtypes to Lender's buildings, and some are atypical. The main characteristic is the number of axes - the building with centrally located front door and one window on each side is considered to have three axis. Mostly there are three, five or seven, rarely nine or even eleven axes. (Martin, 2014, p. 4)

Figure 3.6: The most typical Lender's building is with five axis (Heina 9, Tallinn) (Martin, 2014, p. 5).

Atypical Lender's buildings may be asymmetrical, have two main entrances (i.e two smaller buildings built together) or have an additional one- or two-floor volume on the courtyard side or on one end that was used as living quarters or for workshop or business purposes. A few of those Lender's buildings situated on street corners have special architectural corner-solutions, for example like towers. Very rarely can a part of Lender's building, namely courtyard-side stairwell, be constructed of limestone. (Martin, 2014, p. 8-11)

Some larger Lender's buildings were constructed for wealthier tenants. Those had more rooms per apartment, including a servant's room and did not have a corridor across the building. These have also much more decorative facades. (Martin, 2014, p. 8-11)

Art Nouveau features – bay windows, high stairwell windows with small square frames etc – became more popular on the Lender's buildings right before the WWI (Martin, 2014, p. 12).

After the WWI, the construction of this building type fell back, although some of its features continued to be used in successive buildings even when apartments there were designed larger (Martin, 2014, p. 12). Also, similar apartment buildings with only some differences were constructed in other towns in Estonia but in those cases they are not called the Lender's buildings.

3.3.2. Wooden apartments of 'Tallinn' type

The other building type is so inherent exclusively to Tallinn that it's even called the 'Tallinn' building style. These wooden apartment buildings were constructed in 1920-1930s and are characterized by one central stairwell made of brick. This building type was designed to be rented mainly to upper working-class and middle-class families but there are also some with very large, bourgeois apartments (Kalamees, et al. 2011, p. 29).

Those buildings are constructed of limestone (foundation and plinth), planks or wooden truss and bricks (stairwell). The bricks were made in a local factory in Tallinn. The facade can be covered in wooden boarding or with plaster. On rare occasions the stairwell may be constructed of limestone or granite (Sepp, 2010, p. 9). The roof type can be hip, jerkinhead, gambrel or mansard. More decoratively designed buildings have complicated facade boarding schemes, bay windows, elaborate portals or more detailed window frame schemes. The double-winged front door was never plain, and the transom could be very aesthetically designed.

Figure 3.7: The Tallinn buildings. The details and decorative elements vary greatly. (Arumägi, 2015)

The Tallinn buildings have mostly two floors but for a short period also the third was allowed. In some cases, the third floor is positioned inside a high mansard roof to formally follow the regulations but gain additional space for rental apartments. Unlike previous apartment building types, one building now consisted of apartments of different sizes – two- or three living rooms per apartment. Most apartments had a water closet and kitchen with running water, but only larger apartments had a built-in bathroom.

Figure 3.8: The floorplan of a Tallinn's building (Kapi 6, Tallinn) (Sepp, 2010, p. 12).

Many different architectural styles could be used in designs of the Tallinn building – neoclassicism, late Art Nouveau, functionalism, etc. and combinations of them. Depending on the time of construction one could differentiate three periods:

1. Czarist period – built before 1918, so-called early-period buildings;
2. Independency period – built 1918-1935, so-called high-period buildings and
3. After 1935, so-called late-period buildings (Sepp, 2010, p. 3).

High- and late-period Tallinn buildings have cellars that were used as workshops on for small business purposes, but also facilitated a shared laundry room and a bathroom. This meant that the courtyard was free of utilitarian buildings and was used to plant trees or set up flower- and vegetable beds. (Välja, 2012, p. 9, 13)

3.3.3. 'Stalinist' style brick apartment buildings

This architectural style was developed during the 1930s by the totalitarian regime of the Soviet Union, and was originally called socialist realism. The name 'Stalinist style building' or 'Stalinist-era building' has been put into use afterwards, after Jossif Stalin (1878-1953). It must be stressed that Stalinist style apartment building cannot be viewed as a specific type, but a variety of buildings constructed in 1940-1955, both small and massive, wooden and brick. Nevertheless, they share some characteristics that are recognizable. (Välja, 2012, p. 2). In this project, Stalinist style buildings made of brick were selected, and those made of wood were left out.

Figure 3.9: The construction of Stalinist brick apartment buildings in Uue-Maailma in 1950s (Koidu 89 and Virmalise 28, Tallinn). (Välja, 2012, p. 15)

Figure 3.10: Nisu street in Tallinn, Pelgulinn district, presents Stalinist buildings of one stairwell and two storeys that were constructed implementing the first local typical project. Architect Karl Tarvas. (Välja, 2012, p. 7)

The Stalinist style represents aesthetics that derive from the form and details of classicist architecture combining them with national elements (Välja, 2012, p. 2). In Estonia, this type of apartment buildings were built in place of those destroyed in WWII, and constructed mainly to accommodate workers who immigrated from Soviet Russia. Many of the buildings are constructed according to typical projects that were used all over the Soviet Union and some are typical projects that were used more locally in different cities in Estonia. Behind the very decorated facades were often apartments with simple living conditions and little decoration.

Figure 3.11: The floor plan of Stalinist-era building in Kentmanni 18, Tallinn. Apartments with two rooms, all located on one side of the building, is the most common apartment type (Välja, 2012, p. 35).

Figure 3.12: The fragment of the floor plan of a smaller three-storey Stalinist style apartment building (Välja, 2012, p. 36).

Figure 3.13: The fragment of the floor plan of a dormitory-type Stalinist-era apartment building (Välja, 2012, p. 36).

While the larger, more representative Stalinist type buildings were built in the city center, the smaller buildings were built in the suburbs. Stalinist-era introduced a whole new way of urban planning, which is characterized by the arrangement of buildings as an ensembles. Although all the plans for this type of urban development were not implemented, many quarters were left unfinished.

Figure 3.14: The aerial view of Pelguranna district in Tallinn shows large ensembles of perimetrally positioned Stalinist style buildings around central squares, an architect's drawing from 1949 (Välja, 2012, p. 13).

Some of the Stalinist-era buildings in the milieu area of Uue-Maailma still carry on the traditions from 1930s as they have limestone plinth, larger windows and ornamented frieze (Välja, 2012, p. 11). There is also a whole quarter developed that includes projects both from local and Russian immigrated architects and is distinctively Soviet style both in terms of urban planning as well as building type.

3.3.4. Cultural heritage values

Cultural heritage values of named wooden building-types, Lender's and Tallinn, are based largely on the fact that they, respectively, were constructed at the same time-period and for the same target group. Thus, they have the same characteristics, both in exterior and interior, that define each building type as such. Today many of these buildings form large-scale settlements around Tallinn's old town creating a perceptible street and living environment that enables us to grasp the historic way of living in Tallinn, and tell the story of social and urban development, architects' skills, means and ambitions.

List of valuable elements of wooden apartment buildings:

- Urban planning: the buildings are located on the street line; also fence material, style and height and greenery.
- Building height and shape.
- Plinth finish: protruding from the wall; made of limestone; if the stone is clumped or worked on in other decorative ways, or the joints are finished in a decorative manner, the construction material must be exposed. In other cases, plain plastered and painted finish is typical. Some buildings have stone block imitation finish in plaster which is also suitable.
- Wall decoration scheme: most of the boarded apartment buildings have decorative boarding schemes, some have lost it. If there are some decorative elements preserved, i.e., cornices on the stairwell, they are valuable. If the original finish has been changed, the original aesthetics may be reinstated. In case of a new scheme, it must derive from historical examples, according to the original project or historical photos. Plain plastered and painted walls are also suitable.
- Staircase finish: fully plastered and painted stairwell may or may not be the original scheme but is suitable.
- Windows: originally wooden and with double frames; notice also the proportions, frame distribution scheme and openness. Insulated glazing in the inner frame is not forbidden. If they are not preserved, they must be replicated according to historical photos or original project or using historical examples.
- Doors: originally wooden and quite decorative. If the original doors are not preserved, a replica must be made according to historical photos or original project or using historical examples.
- Basement doors and hatches: the basements of Tallinn type buildings were often originally used as workshops, shops or small businesses; thus some have doors on the street side. The original doors and hatches are valuable, if they are not preserved, they must be replicated according to historical photos or original project or using historical examples.
- Roof: chimneys are plastered and painted white; well-proportioned roof hatches are suitable. Roof windows mostly are allowed on the courtyard side but not together with roof hatches. Suitable material is painted standing seam metal roofing. Roof type is hip or gable.
- Eaves: overhanging the wall; covered with painted wooden boards that can form a cornice.
- Rainwater system: the pipes are round.
- Decorations: any remaining original material (if present) is valuable. Boarding scheme and reinstatement of any decorative elements may be considered during retrofitting.
- Plaster and mortar type: originally lime-based, probably containing also some cement.
- Suitable colours and paint-scheme: suitable colours are ochres, such as browns, brownish reds, greens and yellows. The paint scheme must derive from historical examples.

Stalinist style apartment buildings represent a whole new construction method and foreign aesthetics that illustrate metropolitan ambitions and ideological means by which the occupant authority tried to influence local environment.

In addition to the heritage values in aspects of urban planning, the buildings individually hold the knowledge of specific techniques and working methods, materials, skills, aesthetics that were available and/or valued at the time of their design and construction. Original substance is arguably the best in representing those values while a modern replica can never achieve the same effect, exemplifying the values of authenticity.

When a significant amount of a building's material is substituted with modern replicas, the authenticity of the building is irreversibly lost, and one cannot consider it to be a historical building anymore. It is not only the case of bearing structures, but also exterior finishes, windows and doors, roof materials, decorative elements, and in some cases also the interior is of significance. Allowing the light-hearted substitution of historical substance with modern solutions we would slowly turn our milieu-valuable areas into areas that consist of modern buildings which are based on the looks of historical ones, which is contrary to the reason why such milieu-valuable areas were established in the first place.

Retrofitting can endanger heritage values and pose a significant impact on urban environments. Careless decisions can influence one's desire or complacency to live in a building or in a district altogether, thus being the key risk factor in development of historical urban areas. The districts that have lost a critical mass of its historical character, are slowly draining of habitants, whereas those where the historical environment is well preserved have higher interest indicated by increasing real estate prices.

This leads to the conclusion of the need to promote conscious maintenance and careful restoration, to preserve and advance the historical feel and value of those neighbourhoods.

Figure 3.15 (left) shows a 1927 reconstruction project with indication of what the building looked like before (black lines) and what were the intentions (red lines). Figure 3.15 (middle), shows an undated photograph of the same building demonstrating that the 1927 reconstruction project was implemented. Figure 3.15 (right) shows the next reconstruction (unauthorized, probably in the 1990s. The building is insulated, the boarding is plastic, it has smaller, plastic windows, the awning above the front door is modern, and the window there is gone (only a few major changes). The building has lost its authenticity and character and is now categorized as a low-value building

Figure 3.15: An example of a reconstruction that ignores the historical exterior of a Lender's house type building (Koidu 53, Tallinn), situated in a milieu-valuable area of Uue-Maailma (Uukado, 2024, p. 81).

Figure 3.16 (left) shows a drawing from the 1927 reconstruction project. An inventory drawing from 1969 (figure 3.16, middle) shows that the 1927 reconstruction project was largely implemented. There are differences in the proportions and location of windows and the fronton is rebuilt (it was present before the reconstruction in 1927). It seems that there has never been a vertical boarding beneath the 2nd storey windows. The reconstruction in 2004 (figure 3.16, right) raised the eaves to accommodate living quarters in the attic (vertical boarding beneath the eaves implicates the added height), fronton window is vertically stretched, the building is insulated, and the windows are, in addition to being plastic, not following the historic frame distribution scheme. The décor is mostly gone. There are shortcomings in the execution of construction works, and the materials used are low-quality. The rows of windows do not align with neighbouring building (they were originally the same building type). The building has no categorization by its historic value.

Figure 3.16: An example of a reconstruction that tries to replicate the historical look of a Lender's house type building (Väike-Ameerika 27), situated in a milieu-valuable area of Uue-Maailma (Uukado, 2024, p. 112).

The forementioned risk can be minimized by carefully mapping and hierarchizing the values of a building and deliberating the retrofit solutions that are compatible with the materials and look of a historical building. With that said, it must also be acknowledged, that each building is slightly different and situated in a different context, not to mention the expectations, ambitions and financial means of the owners that all must be considered while compiling this complex system of historical and cultural values. This is the reason that one cannot give an exhaustive list of historical and cultural values that apply to all buildings alike, even when they are of the same type.

List on valuable elements of 'Stalinist' style brick apartment buildings:

- Ensemble: the buildings in this ensemble are of the same construction type, architecturally alike and carry the same (decorative) elements. This includes also the height and shape of the buildings and proportions of different elements in one building.
- Urban planning: the buildings are located on the street line; also fence material, style and height and greenery.
- Plinth finish: protruding from the wall. When not plastered and the construction material, often clumped limestone, is exposed, the original material and aesthetics is valuable. Can be also plastered and painted, decorated as imitating stone blocks.
- Wall decoration scheme: most of the small Stalinist style apartment buildings have plain walls but there may be decorated corners that imitate stone blocks in plaster. Some Stalinist style apartment buildings have their (mostly first-floor) exterior walls decorated. For example, they can have stripes in the plaster or stone-imitating blocks modelled out of plaster on the corners. In this case the original aesthetics is valuable.

- Windows: originally wooden; notice also the proportions, frame distribution scheme and opening type. Typically, there are no elaborate profiles or metal attachments (cremones etc.) but if present, those are valuable as original elements and/or as a database for replicas. Insulated glazing is not forbidden. If original windows are not preserved, they must be replicated according to historical photos or original project or using historical examples.
- Doors: originally wooden; balcony and front doors should be of similar style, and both must remain located deep inside the facade; if they are not preserved, they must be replicated according to historical photos or original project or using historical examples.
- Small open balconies: protruding from the wall or cuts into the facade above the front door; considered less practical and more as a decorative element that is used to architecturally structure the facade; notice the light, airy metal railings and including consoles, if present.
- Roof type and material and the overall roof-landscape: chimneys, ventilation shafts and (if present) small roof hatches are characteristic. Skylights are mostly not forbidden. Roof type is hip or gable. Suitable materials are fibre cement roofing sheets or standing seam metal roofing.
- Eaves: overhanging the wall; often decorated with plastered cornices and consoles which aesthetics and material is valuable.
- Rainwater system: the pipes are round.
- Decorations (if present; cornices, medallions, consoles, framings around the windows and doors etc.): an inseparable part of this architectural style. Their authentic material (could be stucco, plaster, concrete, rarely limestone), scale and position on the building is valuable. In case of building with minimal decorations with simple geometrical forms then their authentic material is not as valuable, but in case of insulating the exterior walls, the location, shape and proportions must be replicated with the material of the same type.
- Plaster type: cement-based, although it may contain also some lime.
- Suitable colours and original paint-scheme: a new-classicist style buildings facade was painted with pastel colours like light yellow, light green, light grey or pink. Decorative elements are mostly painted white. Paint type must be suitable with and durable on a cement-based plaster.

3.4. Case study selection

The 5 case study buildings were selected so that they would be representative for the three culturally valuable archetypes of the neighbourhood (the Lender and Tallinn type wooden buildings and the Stalinist type masonry buildings). The building envelope solutions, service systems and modifications in the current case study buildings also cover a wide variety of possibilities found in Uus Maailm.

3.4.1. Kristiina

General information

Street:	Kristiina
Building year:	1958
Surface:	2898 m ²
Apartments:	34

Architectural information

Archetype:	Stalinist brick apartment building
Construction type:	Brick masonry
Level of protection:	Milieu valuable

Figure 3.17: Facade of Kristiina case (Klõšeiko, 2024e).

Description of the current state

The building is located in a milieu-valuable area of Uue-Maailma and is a part of an ensemble forming two almost complete quarters that follow the urban planning principles of Soviet era.

The walls of the building are brick masonry while the plinth is made of limestone. The structures have largely remained original, while the facade was replastered and repainted ca 10 years ago. The attic is unused, its floor has been insulated using blown wool. The basement was used for storage but has been converted to bicycle parking.

Figure 3.18: aerial view of the Kristiina surroundings (Bing, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is connected to district heating network, while individual gas boilers provide hot water. It does not have mechanical ventilation and some inhabitants complain about air quality

3.4.2. Sikupilli

General information

Location:	Sikupilli
Building year:	1958
Surface:	554.3 m ²
Apartments:	8

Architectural information

Archetype:	Stalinist brick apartment building
Construction type:	Masonry with a cavity
Level of protection:	Milieu valuable

Figure 3.19: Facade of Sikupilli case (Klõšeiko, 2024d).

Description of the current state

The building is in a milieu-valuable area of Sikupilli and also a part of a milieu-valuable ensemble. The buildings in the Sikupilli milieu-valuable area are built between 1940-1950 and follow the principles of Stalinist era urban planning and neo-classicist aesthetics. The construction projects used came from architects from Russia, not locally. The case study building lacks the rich décor of similar houses nearby built some years earlier as cost efficiency was becoming more prioritized.

The masonry walls of the building used to contain an air cavity, which has now been filled with PUR foam (ca 5 years ago) to conserve energy and improve thermal comfort. Attic and basement have been partly converted to extensions of 2nd and 1st floor apartments respectively. Insulation in the attic is suspected to be lacking due to low thermal comfort both in winter and summer. 1 apartment has installed interior insulation. During the facade restoration ca 5 years ago, the basement walls were waterproofed and insulated from the outside.

Figure 3.20: Aerial view of the Sikupilli surroundings (Bing, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated, and hot water is generated, using gas boilers (separately for every apartment). Some apartments also use a fireplace and electrical underfloor heating. 1 apartment has installed an air-to-air heat pump. The building does not have mechanical ventilation.

3.4.3. Koidu

General information

Street:	Koidu
Building year:	1931
Surface:	381 m ²
Apartments:	7

Architectural information

Archetype:	Tallinn type wooden apartment building
Construction type:	Horizontal log with wooden cladding
Level of protection:	Milieu valuable

Figure 3.21: Facade of Koidu case (Klõšeiko, 2024a).

Description of the current state

The walls have mostly retained their original structure, although in some apartments they are insulated with ca 4 cm wood fiberboard. The attic has been converted to apartments along with installing new roofing and insulation. The basement is currently used as storage spaces, and contains a sauna, while it has previously also housed a small shop. The floor between the basement and first floor is partly insulated with cellulose insulation. The windows are a mix of restored original, soviet era and modern windows with varying condition and performance.

Figure 3.22: Aerial view of the Koidu surroundings (Bing, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

Gas heating is used in most apartments, while 2 apartments use wood burning stoves and electrical radiators. The building does not have mechanical ventilation.

3.4.4. Komeedi

General information

Street:	Komeedi
Building year:	1932, 1938
Surface:	239 m ²
Apartments:	4

Architectural information

Archetype:	Wooden apartment building
Construction type:	Horizontal log with wooden cladding
Level of protection:	Milieu valuable

Figure 3.23: Facade of Komeedi case (Klõššeiko, 2024b).

Description of the current state

Although not being a typical Lender or Tallinn type wooden apartment building, the solutions and era are similar to the archetype. Compared to the Tallinn type building, the staircase is wooden, not masonry. The walls are made of horizontal logs and are covered with wooden cladding. The building was constructed in two stages (hence 2 construction dates) and initially housed the owner's family. The windows have partly been replaced with modern ones of different types, quality and performance. Interior insulation is used in some apartments.

Description of the technical equipment

Air-to-air heat pumps are used to heat two apartments, while another two use stove heating. Natural ventilation does not have specific air intakes and relies on air leakages - something that replacing the windows with modern ones has hampered and also negatively affected indoor air quality.

Figure 3.24: Aerial view of the Komeedi surroundings (Bing, n.d.).

3.4.5. Pilve

General information

Street:	Pilve
Building year:	ca 1940
Surface:	556 m ²
Apartments:	6

Architectural information

Archetype:	Tallinn type wooden apartment building
Construction type:	Horizontal log with ventilated plaster
Level of protection:	Milieu valuable

Figure 3.25: Facade of Pilve case (Klõšeiko, 2024c).

Description of the current state

The building is of Tallinn type wooden apartment building and the walls are made of horizontal logs. However, the facades have been covered with a plaster layer on top of a wooden boarding, which is separated from the log wall with an air gap and tar paper. The windows have partly been replaced with modern ones of different types, quality and performance. Interior insulation is used in some apartments. Attic is converted to apartments, while basement is currently unheated and contains storage spaces (although has previously been used as living space too).

Figure 3.26: Aerial view of the Pilve surroundings (Bing, n.d.).

Description of the technical equipment

Gas heating is used by every apartment separately, two apartments additionally also use stove heating, and one apartment uses electrical underfloor heating. Similarly with previous case, ventilation is natural and depend on air leakages.

4. Italy

Author(s): Alessia Buda (PoliMI)

4.1. Relevance of studied typology

Italy's historical building typologies showcase a rich panorama of architectural styles and traditions, reflecting the diverse cultural and historical influences across the country.

What makes the historic centres of Italian cities recognizable is the use of a common architectural language characterized by narrow streets, closed courtyards and multi-storey buildings that create a harmonious urban fabric. These elements often include features such as arches, balconies and decorative stonework that resonate with Italy's rich architectural heritage. Despite these commonalities, each city features unique construction techniques and materials, shaped by local resources and historical contexts.

According to the exceptional cultural and architectural value of many historic townhouses, Italy boasts numerous historic centres that are protected by UNESCO as World Heritage Sites, underscoring their global cultural significance. Each of these cities offers a unique glimpse into Italy's rich past, with well-preserved monuments, buildings, and urban layouts that date back centuries. UNESCO's recognition helps ensure that these historic centres receive the necessary protection and conservation efforts to maintain their integrity for future generations.

For this reason, it was decided to work on one of the historic centres protected by UNESCO, Mantova, where the building peculiarities on a district scale are more recognizable and repeatable. Indeed, in Mantova we can find a common north-Italian historic building typology that is that of masonry heritage townhouses in Northern Italy predating 1945, representing more than 5% of the buildings in Italy.

As highlighted in the building typological studies by the scholars Gianfranco Caniggia and Gian Luigi Maffei (1979 and 1984), masonry townhouses in Northern Italy are characterized by their robust structural systems, typically composed of brick or stone walls with wooden beams supporting the floors and roofs. The choice of materials often depended on local availability, with brick being more common in urban areas and stone prevalent in rural settings. These materials not only provided durability but also contributed to the thermal efficiency of the buildings. The facades of these townhouses often feature symmetrical designs with a clear hierarchy of openings. Windows and doors were strategically placed to enhance natural light and ventilation while maintaining the structural stability of the walls. Decorative elements, such as cornices, string courses, and arched lintels, reflected the stylistic influences of different periods. Caniggia and Maffei's studies highlight the importance also of the relationship between individual buildings and the broader urban context. Narrow, elongated plots often led to the development of deep, multi-storied buildings with internal courtyards or gardens, providing private outdoor space in densely built environments. Over time, many masonry townhouses underwent functional adaptations to accommodate changing living standards and technological advancements.

According to this premise, the preservation of masonry heritage townhouses in Northern Italy is to be considered crucial for maintaining the historical and cultural identity of a part of the Italian heritage. These buildings offer valuable insights into past construction techniques, urban planning principles, and social structures.

4.2. Neighbourhood selection

The UNESCO old town of Mantova is bound at a territorial level by the presence of the Mincio river which delimits the development of the historic centre, connected to the remaining part of the city through three bridges and which includes from the Renaissance settlements to the compact expansions built up until the first half of the 1900s.

Thanks to its historical city centre of great landscape and architectural value, in July 2008 Mantova was registered in the list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites, as a serial site in tandem with the city of Sabbioneta (32 COM 8B.35). In particular, in the 15th and 16th centuries, the renovation of Mantova by the Gonzaga family through urban planning, architectural and hydraulic engineering works saw the contribution of famous architects such as Leon Battista Alberti and Giulio Romano and painters such as Andrea Mantegna, who made Mantova an eminent capital of the Renaissance.

The UNESCO restricted area of the city of Mantova today includes the consolidated historical area of the city which almost faithfully follows what in the Territorial Government Plan (PGT) of Mantova (2022) is indicated as the 'nucleus of ancient formation'.

This area is of great sensitivity both with regards to interventions on buildings (subject to landscape or monumental protection provisions), to maintenance of the public space (often characterized by fine flooring and greenery) and to management of vehicular mobility.

In the Mantova's centre many public administrative services, public establishments, and neighbourhood businesses, as well as tourist flows are concentrated.

At the same time, approximately 17,500 inhabitants live in the historic centre, equal to 36.9% of the resident population. According to ISTAT (Istituto Nazionale di Statistica, trans. *National Institute of Statistics*) data in 2024, most of these homes were built before 1919 and consist of single-family or two-family solutions on two/three floors with more than 4 rooms per apartment and in medium conservation condition.

4.2.1. Mantova's city centre historical evolution

As indicated in the work of Bersani & Bogoni (2008), Mantova developed in the Etruscan period starting from the *civitas vetus* (now Piazza Sordello) marked by the *fossatum bovum* (via Accademia and Cavour today), to which the first walls circle corresponds.

Later, with the Bonacolsi family who took power and established a lordship, the Erbe and Broletto squares and the related palaces of power were built (e.g. Palazzo del Podestà, Palazzo della Ragione); the second wall circle ends with the Rio, the watercourse created by the hydraulic engineer Alberto Pitentino.

With Francesco I Gonzaga the city expanded further to south, reaching the third walls circle, up to including the island of Te. Palazzo Ducale was expanded, the oldest neighbourhood demolished and transformed into a square, the road axes redesigned to build a sumptuous scenography suitable for the representation of the power of the new rulers. The sequence of the three walls circles and the visible overlap of styles allows us still today to grasp not only the progressive expansion of the city at that time, but also its transformation, functional to the new Renaissance idea of the city.

At the beginning of the 18th century, the city of Mantova came under Austrian rule and was thus transformed into a military fortress. Only in the second half of the 1700 the city had a rebirth, also thanks to the construction and completion of numerous palaces (e.g. The Bibiena Scientific Theatre, the Teresiana Library and the Academy of Fine Arts), also witnessed in the Ranieri topographic map of 1831 (Figure 4.2). After other war vicissitudes for the Franco Habsburg domination and the annexation to the kingdom of Italy in 1866, some marshy areas of the city were reclaimed (Piazza Virgiliana and Pajolo area) (Camerlenghi & Caprini, 2019).

In the 20th century, the city underwent another series of transformations due to the desire and need to expand, to grow from an economic point of view and to welcome new industries into the area. Between the 1920s and 1930s the main action concerned the demolition of the old neighbourhoods, convents and churches which have been abandoned for some time, as the Jewish Ghetto near Piazza delle Erbe; in place of the historic districts, large new buildings were built in the rationalist style characteristic of the time (Camerlenghi & Caprini, 2019).

After the bombs of the Second World War, Mantova lost some of its palaces; only in the 60s began a process of economic recovery linked to the introduction of large industries and the construction of new residential neighbourhoods, expanding the city also beyond the river.

Figure 4.1: Extract of the PGT, indicating the Mantova old town and landscape (Comune di Mantova, 2022).

Figure 4.2: Mantova topographic historic map drawn by Giuseppe Ranieri (1831).

4.2.2. Environmental city planning

In recent years, the city of Mantova has been subject to various urban studies aimed at resolving the current socio-environmental and climatic critical issues on a territorial scale. In 2018 the study 'Resilient Mantova: Guidelines for climate adaptation', approved by City Council Resolution, settled a priority for action against heat waves in urban areas, connected to extreme rain events, hydrogeological risks and to those deriving from drought and water shortage. Furthermore, in 2020, the Horizon 2020 project 'INNOVATE Integrated Solutions for ambitious energy refurbishment of private housing project' dedicated to the energy efficiency of private buildings, also ended (Lucertini et al., 2018).

Another important milestone achieved in 2022 was the signing between public and private entities of the Alliance for Carbon Neutrality of Mantova in the Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate: the objective is to achieve carbon neutrality of the territory of the province of Mantova by 2030, which means that carbon emissions into the atmosphere will have to be counterbalanced by the absorption of the carbon itself (Citycalculator, 2023).

Figure 4.3: Extract of the PGT about Mantova old town climate adaptation (Comune di Mantova, 2022).

4.2.3. The District heating network

Mantova is among the top Italian cities for the volume of buildings connected to district heating. The supply of heat by the district heating network takes place through the recovery of industrial heat, supplied by the Versalis thermoelectric power plant.

The share of heat per DH recovered by Versalis constitutes an important contribution to the reduction of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere, which has been growing over time, going from 35% of the total heat supplied in 2005 to a percentage above 70% in recent years. About the thermal energy from DH, it is estimated that 90% of that is supplied to residential users (Gabrielli, 2019).

Figure 4.4: Mantova historical centre, district heating map (Buda, 2024e).

4.2.4. Climate and constructions

According to the Köppen map, the Mantova area falls in the Cfa - Humid Temperate climate band (in Italy it is identified in the climate zone E with 2388 HDD). It is characterized by a humid temperate climate with hot, humid summers, with average temperatures low in winter ($-1/2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and high in summer, on average around 28°C . The wide annual temperature and humidity range justify the large use in the history of the city of terraced constructions, designed to further isolate from the cold and the scorching sun.

Figure 4.5: Average High and Low Temperatures (left) and Average Humidity Comfort Levels (right) in Mantova (Climate Data, 2024).

4.3. Archetype selection

The analysis of the building typologies in Mantova was based on a typological-evolutionary process, on a rather complex cognitive framework, which involves age of construction, material-construction characteristics, methods of aggregation and urban morphology.

Historic buildings in the centre of Mantova have been subject to a slow and progressive evolution over time, not dictated by the application of written regulations, but rather by rules linked to the builders' experience, according to the availability of local materials and the related available technological solutions.

To proceed with the search for archetypes, it was necessary to divide the areas of the historic centre in relation to their own historical and construction peculiarities, as indicated in the PGT map - art. D13 'Residential fabrics, ancient formation nuclei' (Figure 4.6):

A1 - CIVITAS VETUS' CITY OF THE FIRST CIRCLE (11th -12th centuries)

The oldest nucleus of Mantova is characterized by the emergencies of Piazza Sordello and the museum complex consisting of Palazzo Ducale, the Castle of San Giorgio and a significant system of open spaces. On the edge of this area there are closed and dense blocks, defining a continuous curtain on squares and streets, with the prevalence of solids over voids, reduced to small courtyards or shafts.

A2 - SUBURB OF THE FIRST AND SECOND CIRCLE (13th - 14th and 15th -19th centuries)

Urban development of medieval origin, consolidated in the Renaissance era, characterized by dense and compact blocks that define a continuous building curtain on the street front. Streets are designed by buildings, following the non-rectilinear layout typical of the medieval era and creating a homogeneous road profile, despite the different height of buildings gutter lines. The streets trend is conditioned by the presence of the Rio, which divides the city and unites upper and lower lake, as well as by the physical and topographical structure of the portion of land on which the city was formed.

In this central area of Mantova, many buildings are made up of gothic lots on which the building type of the Mantovan terraced house insists. This building typology is still recognizable even if it has been partly modified with the merging of two or more lots to create houses in line by the union of two or more terraced houses (with a relative increase in height) or to create courtyard buildings of a later period.

In the main streets of Mantova, the continuous curtain street front presents a system of porticoed shop-houses: elongated houses with two or three floors, arranged next to each other, with private apartments on the upper floor and the deposits or warehouses on the ground floor. For example, in Corso Umberto the porticoes have 162 columns, erected between 1444 and 1484 by the marquises Ludovico and Federico Gonzaga. They were not built from scratch but derive from the reuse of pre-existing columns; along today's via Broletto around 1190 the Benedictine monks built a series of shops, equipped with front porches, with the intention of renting them. The entrance to each shop coincided with a single arch of the portico, eight feet wide by eight feet deep. The span of the medieval portico was respected during subsequent renovations, and the same original measurements are still found today.

A3 - AREAS WITH CHARACTERISTICS OF CONTINUITY WITH THE UNESCO AREA

Urban development partly like the previous one, i.e. with dense and compact blocks that define a continuous building curtain on the street front mainly made up of Gothic lots on which the building type of the Mantovan terraced house stands, and partly composed of building typologies of the nineteenth-century and twentieth century villas.

Figure 4.6: Mantova PGT map showing the subdivision in three ancient formation nuclei (art. D13) (Buda, 2024e).

According to the expressed analysis, the investigation is focused on few different and prevalent archetypes of masonry buildings in the UNESCO area of Mantova, as listed in the following sections.

4.3.1. Gothic Lot

The Gothic lot archetype is a Medieval typology recurrent in Italy, as a townhouse typology with several variants. It consists in a house with curtain on road, with narrow front and medium length greater than the width. On average, this building typology has three-storey above-ground levels.

On the back of the house, there is generally an inside courtyard which was the latrine since the toilets were not inside the housing units. At the end of the courtyard there were rustic houses for sheltering wood and farm animals, which in many cases are not more existent.

The facade is scanned depending on the width of the lot, but in general there's an access door placed on the side, flanked by one or two windows on the ground floor, while on the upper floors there are two or a maximum three windows of major dimensions.

According to the different scanning given by the access door, the two windows on the ground floor are often not aligned with those on the upper floors, aligned instead.

Spatial organisation

The spatial arrangement of a Gothic lot is distinguished by a specific and functional architectural configuration that meets the urban and social needs of the time. The interior space is characterized by a narrow facade and a medium length that exceeds its width, a distinctive feature reflecting the constraints of medieval urban spaces.

Within the house, the stairs play a crucial role in spatial organisation. These can be placed lengthwise along the lot or centrally positioned. The choice of stair placement is not purely aesthetic but responds to practical and functional considerations: when placed longitudinally, the stairs allow direct and continuous access to the various floors, while a central position facilitates natural lighting and ventilation of the dwelling through the stairwell.

Another key element is the internal courtyard located at the back of the house. This open space, often partially covered, served as a place for daily household activities and included the latrines, thereby ensuring a minimum level of hygiene and privacy. The internal courtyard not only provided a breathing space within the dense urban fabric but also constituted an important source of light and air for the internal environments.

Above the stairs, usually in the middle of the lot, there was an internal shaft that served as a light well. This architectural element had the function of bringing natural light into the house, overcoming the limitations of narrow facades and the surrounding dense constructions. The light well represents a refined example of how Gothic architecture exploited every possibility to improve living quality through innovative solutions.

Variants

The Mantovan Gothic lot exhibits numerous variations, which pertain to spatial changes and responses to different historical needs. It is not uncommon in Mantova to verify the addition of 'porticos': in porticoed-houses the ground floor is entirely dedicated to the public walk, and the building is open on two sides; private apartments are situated at the upper levels.

Figure 4.7: Floor plans and facades of Gothic lot archetype (Buda, 2024f).

Figure 4.8: Porticoed-gothic lot archetype example. Commercial ground-level may include also a mezzanine, accessible from inside the shop. The upper levels are accessed through a staircase positioned in the back side courtyard (Buda, 2024f).

4.3.2. Extended building typology / Houses in line

Another Mantovan building archetype is the extended building typology (or houses in line typology), which morphology may be the result of merging two or more gothic lots, Generally, it has a squared/rectangular planimetry with one or two entrances on the facade, where the second was delegated to the entrance of carriages and is now a driveway. It stands out above all because the facade is messy with multiple openings and the presence of balconies.

Spatial organisation

The building has two/three-storey above-ground level, which was dedicated to commercial purposes. From a stylistic point of view, it does not present a particularly rich facade. In this building variation, despite the not symmetrical facade, the internal structure may result quite symmetrical. Indeed, stairs to access the main floors are placed in the central part of the building and at all levels all rooms are communicating.

Figure 4.9: Floor plan (left) and facade (right) of the extended building archetype (Buda, 2024f).

4.3.3. Palazzetto

It has been used the term 'Palazzetto' to define 17th - 19th century buildings that resembles a Gothic lot but with a greater width, without having connotation typical dimensions of a palace. This classification does not exclude that the building derives from the recast of Gothic lots no longer present (even in the nineteenth-century map of Raineri).

The name also refers to small Liberty buildings (beginning 20th century), when they do not have a dimension of an impact with the road front identifiable as a palace.

Palazzetto building consists of three / four-storey, included the mezzanine and the basement, with a tidy facade of greater dimensions of a house on gothic plot. The entrance is made through a door, that in some case may be larger, due to the historic use for carriages.

Spatial organisation

Internally this building typology has a length distribution; often there is a division of the rooms that varies in relation to the history of the building, showing more recent changes.

Rooms overlook an internal shaft, presenting internal windows / openings.

The first floor, the so-called noble floor, had a greater inter-storey space than the other levels and it was dedicated to welcoming guests and as residence of the lords. The ground floor was dedicated to service spaces; the basement for food supplies and warehouses; the second floor was always dedicated to residential spaces and the attic was generally inhabited by workers.

At the back of the building, just like in the Gothic lot, there is an internal courtyard. Sometimes the building, which in more noble cases may feature elegant balconies on the internal facade, has an extension in plan forming an L, which winds out onto the courtyard.

Figure 4.10: Floor plans and facade of Palazzetto archetype (Buda, 2024f).

4.3.4. Courtyard building

The Mantovan courtyard buildings are palaces that present an even more important character and an adjoining courtyard, around which the building complex develops as a court facility. In this type of building, the structure is made of solid bricks and wooden floors. Building development is on two / three levels, included the mezzanine and the basement.

Spatial organisation

Typically, courtyard buildings are built around a threshing floor or a courtyard and which have a driveway entrance from the street via a portal, which leads through an open corridor that reaches the internal courtyard. There are also more complex ones, where inside there are alleys or other doors that connect multiple internal courtyards, as a recast of several lots. Rooms overlook the central courtyard. The internal subdivisions are also the result of subsequent remodelling of the building; despite this, communication between the different rooms remains.

The complex management of the different levels, consequence of historical stratifications, is delegated to a vertical distribution through multiple stairs: elegant staircases served the main floor and the most important apartments; secondary and narrower stairs, however, served the service spaces.

Figure 4.11: Floor plans and facade of courtyard building archetype (Buda, 2024f).

4.4. Case study selection

A few case studies have been selected to carry out a long-term measurement of temperature and IAQ. Additionally, selected case study buildings will be used for short-term in situ tests and interviews, as described in the technical sheets that follow.

Figure 4.12: Selected case studies are indicated in the Mantova historical centre map, where the UNESCO perimeter is highlighted by a red dotted line (Buda, 2024e).

4.4.1. via Montanara e Curtatone house

General information

Street:	via Montanara e Curtatone
Building year:	17 th century
Surface:	500 m ²
Occupants:	unoccupied since 2023

Architectural information

Archetype:	Palazzetto
Construction type:	Masonry building with wooden floor
Level of protection:	UNESCO protection area; PGT Areas with very high landscape sensitivity - A2: Suburb of the first and second circle, art. D43, D44, D45

Figure 4.13: Facade of via Montanara e Curtatone (Buda, 2024d).

Description of the current state

Building from the early 17th century, it corresponds to the typology of the Palazzetto. With three floors above ground, plus a basement and attic, the building has a three-openings rhythm on the facade, without presenting any other decoration.

The building planimetry is developed in depth. The structure is made of solid bricks with exposed wooden floors and a sloping roof with ancient wooden trusses. At the top, there is an open turret with an ancient wooden double pitch roof structure and small openings on the top of the walls, which help to ventilate and bring more light into the rooms. An internal courtyard/garden at the back allows the rooms to gain more sunlight.

The vertical distribution takes place via an historical staircase in stone located in the middle of the lot. In the middle of the building planimetry there is an atrium which is now glazed, but which was once open to the outside and allowed the sun to enter the rooms: two historic windows, with ancient glass panels bound in lead alloy, embedded in the masonry, testify this ancient use of the internal atrium. The rooms are mostly frescoed and the plaster false ceiling has a reed grip structure underneath. Many of the windows were replaced in the 80s with wooden frames and double glazing.

Figure 4.14: Aerial view of via Montanara e Curtatone surroundings. (Google, n.d.-a).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is not in use, so technical equipment is not functioning. However, previously the building was divided into 6 apartments; in each of them there was a gas boiler used both for domestic hot water and for heating and the terminals were radiators. Monitoring will be focused on free-floating mode.

4.4.2. via Giulio Romano house

General information

Street:	via Giulio Romano
Building year:	18 th -19 th century; partial floor reconstruction of the XX century
Surface:	394 m ²
Occupants:	unoccupied in the last 10 years

Architectural information

Archetype:	Gothic Lot
Construction type:	Masonry building with wooden floor
Level of protection:	Art. 45 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 21 L. 1089/39) - Indirect regulatory constraint; PGT Art. D16 - A3 Areas with characteristics of continuity with the UNESCO area

Figure 4.15: Facade of via Giulio Romano (Buda, 2024c).

Description of the current state

Gothic lot building with an internal courtyard, having three levels. Depicted in Ranieri's historical map (1831), the building retains the characteristics of a neoclassical construction with solid bricks, wooden floors, a plaster false ceiling, and an underlying wattle structure. Part of the first and second floor (those overlooking the courtyard) were rebuilt as a brick and concrete slab in the 1950s after being damaged during the WWII. The facade features a pair of openings, with the historic wooden door still serving as the entrance today. From it, one enters a long corridor leading to the internal courtyard at the rear.

No longer in use for some years, the rooms are distributed vertically via a stone staircase with shaped steps of architectural and historical value. The ground floor, once a service space, is now divided into a bedroom and a living room; two small spaces overlooking the courtyard, once external bathrooms, are now a kitchen and bathroom. The upper floors follow the same pattern, creating two further apartments divided into smaller spaces recently. Many windows were recently replaced with wooden frames and double glazing; internal and external wooden shutters were also replaced, while the decorative pilasters of the stone facade remain.

Figure 4.16: Aerial view of via Giulio Romano surroundings (Google, n.d.-a).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is not in use, so technical equipment is not functioning. However, previously the building was divided into 4 apartments; in each of them there was a gas boiler used both for domestic hot water and for heating and the terminals were radiators. Monitoring will be focused on free-floating mode.

4.4.3. Canonica S. Leonardo

General information

Street:	piazza San Leonardo
Building year:	16 th century, modified during the following centuries
Surface:	286 m ²
Occupants:	5 adults (max 15 in special occasions)

Architectural information

Archetype:	Extended building typology
Construction type:	Masonry building with wooden floor
Level of protection:	art. 10 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 1 L. 1089/39) - Direct protection; PGT A2: Suburb of the first and second circle (13 th - 14 th and 15 th -19 th centuries), artt. D43, D44, D45; A3 UNESCO area

Figure 4.17: Facade of piazza S. Leonardo (Buda, 2024b).

Description of the current state

The Canonica has a linear facade with a simple rhythm with a single entrance from the San Leonardo square. Behind the entrance door there is an open, vaulted and frescoed path that leads to the courtyard behind the church. On the left side of this covered passage there is the entrance to the rectory. Bertazzolo's historical map (1596) shows that the basement dates to the late 16th century; several changes occurred in subsequent centuries until its protection registration in 1939.

The archetype is that of the extended building typology with a linear distribution of rooms and common spaces along a central corridor. The staircase is located at the end of this corridor. Constructed of solid bricks and wooden floors, the structure of which is left exposed. Almost all windows have double glass and restored shading systems.

Rooms are distributed vertically via a stone staircase with shaped steps of architectural and historical value. The ground floor presents a living room with a kitchen and three rooms which are full-time occupied. Fragments of frescoes from the late 16th century are visible on the walls at both ground and first floor. The attic, non-accessible and pillared, has a double-pitched roof with a very high inter-storey space. All rooms have brick vaults and are used as common spaces, with small windows that open.

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated by a methane boiler and each room has a variable number of radiators. The same boiler is also used for DHW. Three splits serve the common areas of the upper floors for the air conditioning.

Figure 4.18: Aerial view of piazza S. Leonardo surroundings (Google, n.d.-a).

4.4.4. Palazzo Vescovile

General information

Street:	piazza Sordello
Building year:	1756
Surface:	535 sqm
Occupants:	2 adults (max 5 people)

Architectural information

Archetype:	Courtyard building
Construction type:	Masonry building with wooden floor and vaults
Level of protection:	art. 10 L. 42/2004 (ex-art. 1 L. 1089/39) - Direct protection; PGT A1: Civitas Vetus, City of the first circle (11 th -12 th century), art. D14

Figure 4.19: Facade of Palazzo Vescovile (Buda, 2024a).

Description of the current state

The Palazzo Vescovile of Mantova was built in the mid-18th century on ancient 14th century buildings and completed in 1765 by the Bianchi marquises with a spectacular pincer staircase and vaulted ceilings decorated with stucco and frescoes. The imposing facade spanning eleven lights is divided horizontally into three bands by string course frames: the smooth ashlar covering the lower band also frames the external and three central bays for the entire height (Introini and Spinelli, 2018).

The building has three levels, plus a basement and an attic, and internal spaces overlook the internal eccentric courtyard. All brick facades are quite symmetrical and have wooden windows, internal tents and external wooden shading systems. The building is actually used by the curia, and it has the diocesan historical archive in the basement. The first floor, dedicated to housing, has an apartment with 5 bedrooms.

Figure 4.20: Aerial view of Palazzo Vescovile surroundings (Google, n.d.-a).

Description of the technical equipment

All rooms are equipped with independent radiators and air conditioners. Heating and DHW are produced with a methane boiler. In anticipation, the client proposed to connect to the city's district heating.

4.4.5. Casa S. Vincenzo

General information

Street:	via G. Chiassi, Guidizzolo (MN)
Building year:	17 th -18 th century
Surface:	408 m ²
Occupants:	6 adults (max 14 adults/children)

Architectural information

Archetype:	Extended building typology
Construction type:	Masonry building with wooden floor
Level of protection:	PGT Comune di Guidizzolo A1: Centro Storico Ambientale - Perimetro di Tessuto Urbano Consolidato

Figure 4.21: Facade of via G. Chiassi in Guidizzolo (Google, n.d.-a).

Description of the current state

The two-level building dates to the founding period of the town of Guidizzolo, which can be attested to around the 17th century. Casa S. Vincenzo is a facility for women and mothers living independently. Inside there are 6 apartments available, today all occupied, which can accommodate up to 14 tenants.

The facade demonstrates a taste that turns towards neoclassical, with openings placed at a constant rhythm, including the driveway that gives access to the courtyard behind. The construction is in solid bricks and wooden floors. The archetype is that of the extended building typology.

The planimetry shows a rectangular and mirror-like layout with respect to the staircase placed in a central position. On each floor there are two apartments with living room-kitchen, bathroom and bedroom. The windows have all been modified with the insertion of double glazing, but the shutters have been maintained.

Figure 4.22: Aerial orthophoto of via Chiassi surroundings (Google, n.d.-a).

Description of the technical equipment

The building is heated by a methane boiler and each room has a variable number of radiators. The same boiler is also used for DHW. Splits serve the single rooms for the air conditioning.

Conclusion

As the research in this report encompasses four different countries, the findings are accordingly diverse. The various cities under investigation - Ghent (Belgium), Trondheim (Norway), Tallinn (Estonia), and Mantova (Italy) - each possess unique histories and socio-economic evolutions. This results in significant differences among the selected neighbourhoods. In Ghent, the neighbourhoods 'Sint-Michielsplein' and 'Vlaanderenstraat - northern part' are examined. The former is an organically developed area dating back to the Middle Ages, featuring a mixture of dwellings from different periods. The latter emerged from 19th-century urban planning, with the Vlaanderenstraat cutting through an old district, and is predominantly composed of 19th-century masonry heritage townhouses with a mixture of commercial and residential functions. In Trondheim, the Baklandet neighbourhood is studied, the first suburb of Trondheim that developed from the mid-1600s. This historic working-class district is characterised by small-scale, wooden log heritage townhouses and vibrant mixed-use buildings. In Tallinn, the neighbourhood of Uue-Maailma is selected for this research. This district primarily consists of apartment buildings constructed to meet the housing needs of workers. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, wooden apartment buildings were predominant, while brick apartment buildings became more common from WWII onwards. The historic city centre of Mantova is a UNESCO World Heritage site, predominantly featuring narrow streets with single-family or two-family dwellings, typically two or three stories high, with more than four rooms per apartment.

In Belgium, four archetypes are defined. The predominant archetype is the middle-class townhouse, common in Ghent as well as other Belgian cities. The other archetypes - the private mansion and the modest house - are less prevalent and the fourth archetype, the multi-family townhouse is rather scarce in Ghent (but frequently present in Brussels and Antwerp). Three case studies are selected: two middle-class townhouses and one private mansion. In Norway, the focus is on a single archetype: the wooden townhouse. Two construction methods are considered: the wooden log and timber frame townhouse. Three case studies are reviewed in detail and five other case studies are listed for further investigation, all conforming the wooden townhouse archetype. In Estonia, two archetypes are considered for this study: the wooden apartment buildings and brick apartment buildings. The former comes in two variants: the Lender and Tallinn style buildings, while the latter is represented by the Stalinist style buildings. Five case studies are selected: two Stalinist style brick apartment buildings, two Tallinn style wooden apartment building and a fifth wooden apartment building. In Italy, four archetypes are described. The first, the Gothic lot, is a medieval small-scale archetype with numerous variants prevalent throughout Italy. The other archetypes, the extended building typology, the palazzetto and courtyard building are of a larger scale. This report examines five case studies: a Gothic lot, two examples of the extended building typology, a palazzetto and a courtyard building.

Key take-aways and Recommendations

The objective of this research was to achieve a transdisciplinary understanding of various heritage buildings and their contexts across different countries. Future work within the HeriTACE project will utilize the selected archetypes, neighbourhoods, and case studies presented in this report to test, simulate, and validate innovative solutions for heating, ventilation, cooling, insulation, and the generation of electricity and heat.

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Annex

Annex A: Interesting case studies Belgium

Street	Facade	Archetype	Information	Heritage value	year of construction
Kwaadham		Middle-class townhouse	co-housing property at the moment. Partly renovated.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	19 th century
Muinklaan		Middle-class townhouse	Partly renovated while retaining heritage value (e.g. new glass). Single-family home. Front yard.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1908
Hendrik van Brederodestraat		Middle-class townhouse	Renovated, with little respect for heritage (much demolished). New extension, windows replaced, roof replaced,	UNESCO buffer zone	?
Sint Kwintensberg		Private mansion	Family house on 0 and 1, student rooms on 2, 3 and attic. Left entrance is for students. Little renovated.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1845

Gebroeders van Eyckstraat		Middle-class townhouse	Single-family house, very large. Replace windows. The facade has clearly been cleaned up already.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1875-1900
Parklaan		Middle-class townhouse	renovated, respecting heritage (glass, WP?, fan convectors, PV,...). nr 34 is still the most original.	ascertained built heritage. Protected cityscape. UNESCO buffer zone	1898
Dendermondsesteenweg		Private mansion	has received a grant for the restoration of a valuable non-protected facade. Beyond city centre.	ascertained built heritage.	1900-1918
Belfortstraat		Private mansion	recently renovated by Element architects into multi-family housing and café, including coach house on the Onderstraat side:	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1907
Belfortstraat		Middle-class townhouse	recently purchased by new owners with heritage reflex. Corner house.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1900-1925

Koningstraat		Middle-class townhouse	Windows seem to have been replaced	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1800-1850
Sluizeken		Multi-family townhouse	Currently catering on the ground floor. Potential b&b deepening. Art nouveau.	Protected monument. Ascertained built heritage. Protected cityscape. UNESCO buffer zone	1904
Hendrik van Brederodestraat		Middle-class townhouse	has already been extensively renovated (e.g. lowering the temperature, insulating the rear facade, replacing windows, PV, ventilation C, etc.). Some errors in the heritage value of the facade (wrong paint, PVC windows)	UNESCO buffer zone	1882
Ferdinand Lousbergskai		Private mansion	single-family home, will soon be renovated.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1859

Sint-Joriskaai		Private mansion	Now multi-family house, used to be just single-family house. A bit too much (similar to Sint Kwintensberg) with their two gates. No left neighbor, so extra heat loss there.	ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone	1875-1900
Edmond van Hoorebekestraat		Modest house	seems rather modest house. Double house. The right neighbour is therefore identically mirrored, but seems to have already been renovated/facade cleaned. Renovation planned.	ascertained built heritage	1875-1900
Karel van Hultemstraat		Middle-class townhouse	Corner house dating from the beginning of the 20 th century, divided into studios/apartments, heritage value, aspires to subsidy remarkable buildings.	ascertained built heritage. Protected cityscape. UNESCO buffer zone	1900-1914
Holdaal		Middle-class townhouse	no neighbor on the left, so extra heat losses there	UNESCO buffer zone	?

<p>Kuipersk aai</p>		<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<p>Fairly homogeneous block of houses with 5 similar middle-class townhouses. Nr 14 is a corner house. 4,8,12 and 14 also merchant's house.</p>	<p>ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone</p>	<p>1875-1914</p>
<p>Coupure</p>		<p>Private mansion</p>	<p>Removal of facade plaster in the 20th century. Replacement of joinery between 1956 and 1977. Preserved 19th-century interior. Currently under renovation where the house is being extended into multi-family house with 5 entities.</p>	<p>ascertained built heritage. Protected cityscape. UNESCO buffer zone</p>	<p>1875-1900</p>
<p>Sint- Martenss straat</p>		<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<p>Single-family house built in 1909. Since 2016 under restoration while retaining its function. Similar house next door, with raised ground floor and 2 spans.</p>	<p>ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone</p>	<p>1909</p>

D5.1 Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels

<p>Kasteellaan</p>		<p>Private mansion</p>	<p>Several mansions on the Kasteellaan. No. 66 converted into a group practice</p>	<p>ascertained built heritage. UNESCO buffer zone</p>	<p>1875-1900</p>
<p>Prinses Clementinalaan</p>		<p>Middle-class townhouse</p>	<p>Front yards. Divided into apartments</p>	<p>ascertained built heritage. Protected cityscape. UNESCO buffer zone</p>	<p>1900-1950</p>
<p>August van Bockxstaelsestraat</p>		<p>Modest house</p>	<p>Contact through partner in project</p>	<p>/</p>	<p>1850-1900</p>